

Deliverable 4.4 Demo Execution Report

APPENDIX A

RIDE2RAIL

**Revealed and Stated Preference Survey for
“Willingness to Accept CARPOOLING”**

FINAL REPORT

October 2022

Acknowledgements

The study team wishes to express their sincere thanks to the ATTIKO METRO SA personnel involved in the supervision of the present research study and the provision of the necessary data and information required for the study purposes.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Aim and Objectives of the Survey

Ridesharing/Carpooling travel options, either as a driver or as a rider, mainly aim at increasing vehicle occupancy and consequently reducing circulation of cars and road traffic. The main target population of ridesharing/carpooling are commuters using their private vehicles on a regular basis. A secondary target are people using other modes, such as suburban public transport, which do not offer a satisfactory level of service, as well as persons who prefer not to travel at all (sleeping demand). Several supplementary measures are usually introduced to facilitate potential car poolers and provide incentives, such as preferential parking, guaranteed ride home, ridesharing/carpooling matching platforms, etc. Given the complexity of this issue, carpooling policies should be both targeted and realistic and need to be based on exhaustive research and targeted studies.

ATTIKO METRO SA (AM), being a partner of the RIDE2RAIL (R2R) European project consortium of the EU Horizon Programme, H2020 EU.3.4.8.4. – “Innovation Programme 4: IT Solutions for attractive railway services”, and having as one of their strategic goals the reduction of single-occupant car trips as well as the reduction of GHG emissions in the areas where it offers urban rail services, procured a service contract for a combined Revealed and Stated Preference (RP/SP) survey aiming at determining the “Willingness to Accept Ridesharing/Carpooling” of commuters in the area of Attica Region. The contract, (TSA 416/22), awarded to POLINDE Consulting Engineers, a transportation consulting firm based in Athens, Greece.

The RP/SP survey was addressed to specific categories of trip makers and more specifically to those who commute from the eastern areas to Athens and vice versa using either the Metro and/or the Suburban rail system in the Attica Region. The main aim of the survey is to determine the willingness of these trip makers to accept to use for their first/last mile of their trip a ridesharing/carpooling alternative either as drivers or as riders, denoted as CPD and CPR respectively. A precondition for a person to be eligible to take part in the survey is to use metro or suburban rail for the main trip segment, whereas the last/first mile trip segment to be made by any means of transport other than on foot. Trip makers travelling on Business trips or on trips using cars provided by their employment are not examined in the survey.

The main objectives of the survey towards the satisfaction of the aim of the awarded contract can be summarised as follows:

- to determine the average Values of Time of potential carpoolers depending on their current trip and personal characteristics;
- to develop mathematical mode choice models for carpooling travel options;
- to estimate the probability of a person having specific trip and personal characteristics to choose among alternative travel options offered to him for the first/last mile of his trip;
- to examine the factors/attributes which have an effect on trip makers’ choices
- to provide useful insights to ATTIKO METRO for drawing the required carpool policies satisfying the goals of the R2R project.

One of the main goals of the survey has been to find an adequate number of metro users willing to take part in the Athens demo site of the RIDE2RAIL project satisfying the selection criteria specified by AM. The demo application is about the use of a platform developed by the RIDE2RAIL consortium

partners enabling commuters using Metro or suburban rail in eastern Attica to find suitable carpooling matches for their trip. More specifically the Athens demo site aimed at:

- enhancing the connection of low density Attica parts to PT modes and specifically to the ATTICO Metro, through the provision of demand responsive ridesharing services
- serving as test site for the platform assessment taking into account new forms of shared mobility,
- evaluating innovative concepts of multimodality

Two applications were developed in the demo site; the “Travel Companion” app and the “Driver Companion” app. The first one was being addressed to persons who do not use a car to reach the metro station or to depart from a station towards their final destination. The second one was for trip makers using their car and looking for a carpool travel companion. In total 151 persons agreed to participate in the pilot applications of the R2R Athens demo.

Synopsis of the RP and SP Survey

The study area selected for this research study is the catchment zone of the 20-km long air-rail corridor between “Doukissis Plakentias” and Athens Airport rail stations along "Attiki Odos" tolled motorway. This area comprises territories of five (5) municipalities with low population densities compared to the core centre of the Athens municipality. The survey was addressed to intermodal hub users, belonging to different categories according to the mode used for the first/last part of their journey. The different modes are the following:

- CAT 1: Public Transport Feeder bus (BUS)
- CAT 2: Driving Alone (SOV) and parking at or outside the designated P&R facilities at the stations
- CAT 3: Driving with one or more passengers (HOV) and parking at or outside the designated P&R facilities at the stations
- CAT 4: Taxi (TAR) from home to Metro/suburban rail station and vice versa.

Users of two metro/suburban rail stations, namely Doukissis Plakentias station and Koropi station were approached for the survey purposes. The survey which was made using a combination of the Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) and of Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI) technique, was completed in two phases. The first was a screening questionnaire to make sure that the persons approached were eligible to participate in the full RP/SP survey and took place at the stations using the CAPI technique. The second phase, being the full RP/SP survey, was completed by the respondents at home or at work using the CAWI technique, with or without the telephone assistance of contractors’ trained personnel.

The survey period had been initially planned for May-June 2022. Given that special emphasis was paid on respondents’ data protections issues, some inevitable delays in the completion of the survey were emerged, thus shifting the survey 5-6 weeks later. An additional short survey was conducted in the first days of September 2020 in order to meet the required sampling targets.

In total some 5,400 persons were approached in the screening (first) phase of the survey, and from those some 2,000 persons were eligible to take part in the second phase. From the eligible participants approximately 1250 agreed to proceed and signed the data protection form and finally 493 persons completed the second phase questionnaire. The completed questionnaires involve:

- 227 Trip makers who travel alone towards the Metro/Suburban rail station.
- 143 Trip makers who use public bus.

- 79 Trip makers who travel by their passenger car together with other riders.
- 44 Trip makers who use a Taxi to reach the station.

The questionnaire used for both phases of the survey was structured in 5 sections as follows:

First Phase	
Section A	General Information and data completed by the interviewer before starting the screening phase questions to the interviewed person
Section B	Screening questions to check whether the person is eligible for the RP/SP survey and assign him/her to the right category (stratum)
Second Phase	
Section C	Revealed Preference Questionnaire. It applies to both inward and outward most common commuting or personal trips of the person interviewed. Depending on the category (stratum) a trip maker falls in, the respective sequence of questions appears
Section D	Socioeconomic characteristics of the person and the household he/she belongs to
Section E	Stated Preference Questionnaire. It includes 8 game cards with three travel options every time with different attribute levels. Attribute figures for each level relate to the travel cost and travel time values corresponding to the person's responses in Section C. The total number of game cards used are 24 which are grouped in three octaves

The travel choice sets and the options (alternatives) offered to the interviewed persons in the SP part of the survey were as follows:

	Travel Option 1 (current)	Travel Option 2	Travel Option 3
Choice Set 1	PT Feeder Bus	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 2	Car Driver (SOV)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 3	Car Driver (HOV)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 4	Taxi Rider (TAR)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider

The attributes included in each travel option were:

- Travel time, for all alternatives
- Travel cost, for all alternatives including parking cost for SOV, HOV, CPD and CPR
- Preferential Parking (Existence or non-existence), only for CPD and CPR
- Meeting Point (Home or Out of home) for CPR
- Flexible time schedule for CPD and CPR

Model results and survey findings

Multinomial Logit (MNL) mixed models were developed for determining the probability a person to make a mode choice among the alternatives offered to him/her. Separate models were developed for Car pool drivers and Car pool Riders for each trip maker category. A model expression was also developed for all categories together. The models are shown the two tables below:

Overview of MNL choice models for choosing CPD travel option for the first/last mile

Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
Bus	$V_{CPD} = 0.14 - 0.92 * COST_{CPD} - 0.11 * TIME_{CPD} - 1.84 * TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons -$

Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
	$0.79*SEX + 0.46* AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.75*AGE.GR.46.55$
SOV	$V_{CPD} = -1.03 - 0.11*COST_{CPD} - 0.05*TIME_{CPD} - 0.28*PARK_{CPD} - 0.55*MEETING_{CPD} + 0.31*HH.SIZE - 0.34*HH.VEH - 1.24*OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative + 1.14*OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.31*OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$
HOV	$V_{CPD} = 0.22 - 0.24*COST_{CPD} - 0.05*TIME_{CPD} - 0.76*PARK_{CPD} - 0.66*MEETING_{CPD} + 0.86*TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week + 1.83*AGE.GR.26.35 - 1.41*AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.67*OCCUP.freelancer + 0.83* HH.SIZE - 1.07*HH.VEH$
Taxi	$V_{CPD} = 1.54 - 0.76*COST_{CPD} - 0.14*TIME_{CPD} - 2.23* TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons + 2.16*AGE.GR.46.55 - 3.88* HH.INC.1500.2000 - 4.83* HH.INC.over.2000 + 1.44*KNOW.CARPOOLING$
All	$V_{CPD} = -2.67 - 0.31*COST_{CPD} - 0.03*TIME_{CPD} - 0.30*PARK_{CPD} - 0.40*MEETING_{CPD} - 0.57*TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week - 0.34*AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.70*AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.35*AGE.GR.56.65 - 1.00*AGE.GR.over.65 + 2.06*OCCUP.retired + 0.20* HH.SIZE + 0.32*HH.INC.1500.2000 + 1.76*OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral + 2.47*OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.80*OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$

Overview of MNL choice models for choosing CPR travel option for the first/last mile

Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
Bus	$V_{CPR} = 1.26 - 0.92*COST_{CPR} - 0.11*TIME_{CPR} - 2.39* TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons - 0.88*SEX - 0.92* AGE.GR.36.45 - 1.20*AGE.GR.46.55$
SOV	$V_{CPR} = -1.08 - 0.11*COST_{CPR} - 0.05*TIME_{CPR} - 0.28*PARK_{CPR} - 0.55*MEETING_{CPR} + 0.24*HH.SIZE - 0.42*HH.VEH - 1.62*OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative + 1.69*OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.98*OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$
HOV	$V_{CPR} = -0.55 - 0.24*COST_{CPR} - 0.05*TIME_{CPR} - 0.76*PARK_{CPR} - 0.66*MEETING_{CPR} + 1.21*TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week + 2.26*AGE.GR.26.35 - 0.93*AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.93*OCCUP.freelancer + 0.89* HH.SIZE - 0.98*HH.VEH$
Taxi	$V_{CPR} = 2.95 - 0.76*COST_{CPR} - 0.14*TIME_{CPR} - 1.68* TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons + 1.47*AGE.GR.46.55 - 4.14* HH.INC.1500.2000 - 4.35* HH.INC.over.2000 + 1.40*KNOW.CARPOOLING$
All	$V_{CPR} = -2.67 - 0.31*COST_{CPR} - 0.03*TIME_{CPR} - 0.30*PARK_{CPR} - 0.40*MEETING_{CPR} + 0.24*TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week - 0.54*AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.83*AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.15*AGE.GR.56.65 - 2.31*AGE.GR.over.65 + 3.60*OCCUP.retired + 0.11* HH.SIZE + 0.31*HH.INC.1500.2000 + 1.30*OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral + 2.39*OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 3.04*OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$

From all travel option specific attributes examined, only “Flexible time schedule for CPD and CPR” was found not statistically significant. All other attributes proved significant and received the correct sign, including “Preferential Parking” and “Meeting Point”. Depending on the model, several trip and individual characteristics proved significant for the persons’ choice.

The willingness to pay values obtained from the developed models are as follows

Willingness to Pay (WTP) for Preferential Parking and Meeting Location (€/hour)

Category		Bus	SOV	HOV	Taxi
Preferential Parking	N/A	2.6	2.7	N/A	
Meeting Location	N/A	5.0	3.2	N/A	

These values are deemed quite logical and in line with other values derived from other similar surveys and studies, or older values corrected/brought to current price levels. The only exception is the VoT of SOV users which is high approximately 80% higher than the average levels obtained from other sources. An explanation to that is the higher income levels of the persons living in the study areas and in addition the fact that the specific first/last mile trip segments are short and thus the VoT is relatively high. This possible explanation is reinforced by the fact that the SOV users park and leave their vehicle for 6-10 hours every day at the station they use to board on the urban rail.

Finally, the travel time and travel cost elasticities calculated for each travel option and each transport mode used by the respondents are presented in the following table.

Travel time and cost elasticities

	Current mode	CPD	CPR
Travel Time Elasticities			
Bus	-0.92	-1.36	-1.17
SOV	-0.42	-0.46	-0.59
HOV	-0.51	-0.45	-0.57
Taxi	-1.14	-1.93	-0.86
All	-0.23	-0.28	-0.29
Travel Cost Elasticities			
Bus	0.00	-10.99	-1.63
SOV	-0.24	-1.01	-0.16
HOV	-0.64	-2.22	-0.36
Taxi	-1.92	-10.46	-0.83
All	-0.41	-3.14	-0.45

From the Table contents, it can be concluded that:

- Bus and taxi users are more affected by an increase in travel time and travel cost for the option of carpooling as a driver.
- SOV and HOV users are less affected by a similar increase in travel time and travel cost for the option of carpooling as a driver.
- For all users' categories, travel cost is more significant than travel time for carpooling as a driver while the opposite applies for carpooling as riders with the exception of bus users.

Other main findings resulted from the survey and the models developed include the following:

- There are no significant differences among male and female trip makers towards the carpooling preferences, except for the bus users' category. Regarding bus users, women seem to be more favourable in becoming carpoolers than men.
- Trip makers coming from households with low number of available vehicles, seem that they are in favour of becoming carpool riders than those who come from households with more

available cars. It seems that the difference between the Car Ownership Index and number of persons holding a driver's license may have an effect on the trip makers preferences.

- Overall, the majority of the persons interviewed are in favour of a carpooling travel option as a rider and then as a carpool driver. This finding is stronger for the persons who have a positive attitude towards carpooling

Conclusions and Recommendations

Ridesharing/carpooling is considered an appealing option for meeting the SHIFT2RAIL goals, especially in cases such the eastern area of Attica Region in Greece. The RP/SP survey carried out in this geographical area indicates that there is a critical mass of trip makers – mainly commuters - who use on a regular basis metro or suburban rail and make the first or the last trip segment by others transport modes and who will be willing to shift to carpooling for this segment either as drivers or riders. Supplementary measures such as preferential parking and carpooling matching platforms have an additive effect. In addition, it is anticipated that induced carpooling demand may result once the right policies are designed and implemented. A successful carpooling policy requires of course among other the examination of technical, legal, social and cultural aspects.

Having all these in mind, the following recommendations may be suggested:

1. The involved authorities/agencies which have the responsibility to implement carpooling schemes in the Attica Region should consider all relevant aspects affecting ridesharing success. Based on the surveys and the choice model results, it turns out that given the right incentives in terms of travel cost, parking cost and availability and tools for finding the most suitable carpool matches, a significant percentage of trip makers who currently use either bus, or car or taxi could become potential carpool drivers or riders.
2. ATTIKO METRO SA, in case they decide to forward carpool plans along with other involved authorities, will have to secure adequate parking spaces close to the metro stations. Furthermore, they will have to assign a study about the parking fees in all stations in conjunction with the incentives they plan to provide.
3. A full-scale study is required in order to determine the volume of potential carpoolers from each geographical area of the Attica Region per category (CAT1, CAT2, CAT3 and CAT4). The study should include an extended RP and SP survey, and should be executed in stages in order to simplify the whole process. Estimation of carpoolers must be based on the new census demographic data and also on recent PT data and ATTIKO METRO models.
4. In addition to the above, mixed car-sharing/carpooling schemes should be studied. Such schemes help overcome certain disadvantages associated with carpooling, since guaranteed ride home stops becoming a major issue.
5. The involved authorities and stakeholders need to examine in depth all technical, legal and technological aspects that turn into real problems if not considered well in advance.

1. Introduction

This is the Final Report of the Revealed and Stated Preference Survey aiming at determining the “Willingness to Accept CARPOOLING” of commuters in the area of Attica Region. The survey was realised on behalf of ATTIKO METRO SA.

The survey is part of the Ride2Rail (R2R) European project of the EU Horizon Programme, H2020-EU.3.4.8.4. - Innovation Programme 4: IT Solutions for attractive railway services. The project has been awarded to a transnational 17-member consortium led by Union Internationale Des Transports Publics (UITP). ATTIKO METRO SA is one of the consortium members responsible for the Athens case study. The project aims among others at reductions of single-occupant car trips, car-kms travelled as well as at GHG emissions.

A main goal of the R2R project has been to test the Athens Demo site consisting of a platform with two applications aiming at finding carpooling matches for car users and travel companions. The design and specifications of this Demo is provided in the respective R2R deliverables

The design and execution of the survey as well as the data processing, analysis and the development of multinomial choice models has been awarded by ATTIKO METRO SA to POLINDE Consulting Engineers, a firm based in Athens, Greece (Contract TSA 416/22).

The report provides an overview of the realised survey including carpooling and first/last mile bibliographic review, the survey design and implementation activities, data processing, descriptive statistics of the sample data, development of multinomial choice models and finally the presentation of findings and their interpretation.

The persons involved in this research study effort and their roles are shown below.

George Lymberopoulos	Project Director	Transportation Engineer
Prof. Panagiotis Papaioannou	Team Leader	Transportation Engineer & Economist
Anna Politou	Project Coordinator	Transportation Engineer & Economist
Antonios-Petros Anagnostopoulos	System Analyst	Electronic Engineer and a Network Specialist
Katerina Rentziou	Assistant Engineer	Transportation Engineer
Georgia Exagoustidou	Assistant Engineer	Transportation Engineer

2. Aim and Objectives of Revealed and Stated Preference Survey

The main aim of the survey is to investigate the willingness of the users of the Metro/Suburban rail system in the Attica Region, who commute from the eastern areas to Athens and vice versa, to accept to use for their first/last mile of their trip a carpooling/ridesharing alternative either as drivers or as riders. The main segment of the trip is always made using Metro or suburban rail, whereas the last/first segment may be made by any means of transport or on foot.

The survey is addressed to specific categories of trip makers. Trip makers travelling on Business trips or on trips using cars provided by their employment are not considered in the survey. More specifically, the following categories of trip makers are eligible for investigation:

1. Trip makers who use for their first segment of their trip from home to work/education facility or to other destination for personal reasons and vice versa for their last mile, Public Transport bus
2. Trip makers who travel their first mile and vice versa their last mile by their passenger car as solo drivers and park their car at a parking facility or on the roads close to the metro/suburban station used to ride the metro or rail
3. Trip makers who travel their first mile and vice versa their last mile by their passenger car with another rider and park their car at a parking facility or on the roads close to the metro/suburban station location
4. Trip makers who travel their first mile and vice versa their last mile by taxi

All persons should be 18 years old or older to take part in the survey. It is expected that the persons who may decide to carpool as an alternative way to travel from home to Metro/suburban rail station or vice versa, will be car owners.

The objectives of the survey can be summarised as follows:

- to determine the average Values of Time of potential carpoolers depending on their current trip and personal characteristics;
- to develop mathematical mode choice models for carpooling travel options
- to estimate the probability of as person having specific trip and personal characteristics to choose among alternative travel options offered to him for the first/last mile of his trip;
- to examine the factors/attributes which have an effect on tripmakers choices
- to provide useful insights to ATTIKO METRO for drawing the required carpool policies satisfying the goals of the R2R project

Additional objectives vis a vis the behavioural parameters of the travellers include:

- determining the average and the min/max Values of Time of carpooling as a driver and as a rider;
- investigating the trade-off between travel time and travel cost for different first/last mile categories of trip makers;
- determining the disutility of carpool drivers associated with detouring in order to pick up carpool riders;
- determining the disutility of carpool riders associated with waiting time/walking distance in order to be picked-up by the carpool;
- determining the Value of (dis)utility of different vs same gender ridemates

3. Brief Literature Review

Rail Public Transport (PT) modal shares in peri-urban low density areas are often disappointing due to the 'first/last mile' problem. This problem pertains to poor bus PT feeder services to/from rail PT stations and/or congested Park and Ride (P&R) facilities at the respective intermodal hubs which hinder access to rail PT stations either by PT or private cars. Shared mobility in the form of carpooling (being a form of ridesharing) is a viable alternative in connection to urban rail, especially when appropriate incentives and ridematching tools are effectuated. Thus, carpooling may complement PT and amplify rail ridership.

Ridesharing, and in particular carpooling, is an efficient mobility form which may fill service gaps to rail stations and other PT terminals. PT gaps are evident in low density areas such as the eastern parts of Attica Region along the rail track towards the Athens International Airport. Affected communities have an interest to enhance low cost accessibility to trunk-haul lines (TCRP, 2012).

According to Furuhata et al. (2013), 'Ridesharing' refers to a mode of transportation in which individual travellers share a vehicle for a trip and split travel costs such as fuel, toll, and parking fees with others that have similar itineraries and time schedules. They consider informal carpools involving family members and related persons (e.g. friends, co-workers) as well as formal carpools involving unrelated persons (unknowns). A slightly different definition from ICARO project final report (ICARO, 1999), states that 'Car-pooling is at least two people riding in a car usually belonging to one of the occupants, whether one person always drives or the carpoolers alternate cars. Each member would have made the trip independently if the carpool had not been there. Driver and passengers know before the trip that they will share the ride and at what time they will be leaving. Professional and/or commercial vehicles are excluded'.

Carpooling is served by private cars for various trip purposes. In a US survey in Texas, 50% of carpool vehicles using High Occupancy Vehicle (HOV) lanes with car carrying two or more occupants were commuters (Li et al., 2007). However, other trip purposes may be also satisfied by the carpool mode such as recreation or shopping.

Ways of filling up mobility needs of people in low density areas are equivalent to solving the 'last-mile' problem in logistics terms. Thus, carpooling is a modal form which complements PT for short-distance rides. In contrast, long-distance carpools fully replace PT rides, thus deteriorating sustainability (Stiglic et al., 2018).

Environmental concerns (e.g. car-kms and GHG emission savings) are further reasons for promoting carpooling and ridesharing in general. Carpools reduce Single-Occupant (SOV) car trips leading both to road and parking decongestion. Less parking-search traffic and need for parking spaces are additional benefits. User concerns (e.g. minimization of car-kms, excess driving time and travel costs) are aligned in this respect with environmental concerns, demonstrating a win-win situation. Car-kms and tons of GHG emission savings as well as increases in car occupancy levels are prevalent KPIs from the community perspective. From the user perspective, appropriate KPIs pertain to excess driving time (delay), travel costs and comfort levels.

Ridesharing platforms and apps are more appropriate for the formation of formal carpools. Large employers' platforms or large trip generators mobility plans (e.g. universities, shopping malls, etc.), may also serve as carpool enabling mechanisms.

Intermodal hubs are a critical component for promoting carpooling in a region. The rail-rideshare combination of intermodal hubs provides a ridematching advantage. The hubs as shared and fixed

trip ends enable shorter detours and less inconvenience for the carpool drivers, thus allowing more feasible ride matches than complete-journey carpools where both trip ends are variable. In case of long journeys, the proportion of trips with similar O-D pairings is small due to the distance friction. The tolerances for detour delays and walk time measure the spatial flexibility of the riders. Narrow departure time windows and schedule rigidity of the carpoolers are further limitations for ridematching. The temporal flexibility of riders (e.g. earliest possible departure time, latest possible arrival time) greatly impacts the ridematching success rate.

3.1. Factors affecting ridesharing behaviour

Prominent factors in the literature having an impact on ridesharing behaviour are:

- **In-vehicle travel time**, perceived differently by carpool drivers and by (incidentally more relaxed) riders. According to Hunt and McMillan (1997), the relationship between the value of time of a rider and a driver for commuters is approximately 0.69.
- **Detour time**, i.e. delay of the carpool driver to pickup and drop-off the rider at a meeting point (home or out-of-home); excess driving time represents an inconvenience factor for the driver. The value of detour time to the value of direct travel time amounts about 1.4 for commuters (Hunt and McMillan, 1997).
- **Walk time** of the rider to an out-of-home meeting point. The value of walk time to the value of in-vehicle travel time amounts about 1.8 in Athens (Spanos et al., 1997)
- **Travel cost** (normally shared equally among car poolers) includes -apart of fuel cost- toll cost and possibly parking cost. The latter is shared equally through the number of car occupants, if they are unrelated; in case of family members or friends, mostly the driver assumes the burden.
- **Type of relationship** between riders (family members, friends/co-workers, unknowns)
- **Availability of and wait time** for a Guaranteed Ride Home (GRH) referring to riders. The value of GRH availability approximates the PT ticket fare for commuters (Hunt and McMillan, 1997). Overall, a return trip outwards, must not be done with the inward driver too.
- **Existence of HOVs** which stipulate time savings to carpoolers by providing exclusive lanes for them.
- **Preferential Parking**, which gives an additional motive to carpoolers, both drivers and riders to choose this travel option.
- **Schedule Flexibility**, ability of carpoolers to adjust their schedules in order to plan their trips. Flexibility is measured in terms of time (how many hours in advance the driver should be notified for the exact time of the next trip should a change in the travel plan has been occurred)

Effective policy incentive for carpooling in conjunction with preferential parking is discounted parking fees. Another incentive is the granting of free PT tickets or even taxi ride to provide the GRH stimulus (Menczer, 2007). A certain factor is the ridematching transaction cost, dependent on the design features of mobile apps. Relevant socioeconomic characteristics pertaining to carpool propensity are home location, age, gender, household size, number of household cars over number of driver licenses, schedule flexibility, activity constraints, mode currently used which reflect inertia of trip makers as well as current direct-trip characteristics.

3.2. P&R facilities

It is well known that parking constraints in central urban destinations generally increase the PT share (Morrall and Bolger, 1996), which is also true for the Athens case (Polydoropoulou et al., 1998).

However, referring to peri-urban areas close to trip origins, Merriman (1998) provided evidence that increases in the capacity of parking-constrained suburban rail stations increase rail ridership. Depending on time period and other variables, the author observes that system-wide between 0.75 and 1.5 additional boarders are associated with an additional parking space. Nevertheless, expansion of parking capacity is cost-intensive and detrimental to a sustainable transit-oriented development around stations. A smarter way to increase rail ridership without expanding parking capacity around suburban stations is to increase ridesharing to P&R hubs. Such an option was studied in Thessaloniki, Greece in 1997, as part of the ICARO project demo case combining carpool use, the implementation of an HOV lane and the provision of a P&R facility (ICARO, 1999). The study findings indicated consistently that an increase in carpooling use is achieved when additional measures such as preferential parking for car poolers are taken.

3.3. SP experiments and carpooling

SP experiments with hypothetical trade-off games have been used in a few studies of carpooling choice behaviour. All concern entire journeys from initial trip origins to final destinations. Experiments for the propensity to participate in carpooling schemes as a driver or as a rider have shown the importance of, inter alia, working schedule flexibility, weather conditions and perceived rider vs. driver profile respectively (Tahmasseby et al., 2016). Correia and Viegas (2011) merge together carpool drivers and riders in the form of a single alternative to driving alone/with family. Higher willingness to carpool characterises younger persons and lower income people. A highly positive and significant Alternative Specific Constant (ASC) represents an unexplained preference for carpooling. Trust-building was intended through the formation of car clubs. Focusing on the home to work trip towards city centre, Van der Waerden et al. (2015) asked car drivers in an SP experiment to choose between driving alone and carpooling, in a similar setting of Correia and Viegas (2011). Most influential is the flexibility of working hours, time and cost variables.

In the SP experiment of Ciari and Axhausen (2012), respondents choose among car, PT, carpooling as driver and carpooling as rider. The experiment is conducted at a nation-wide level in Switzerland covering trips longer than 10 kms, thus carpool alternatives antagonize PT mode by design. The in-vehicle Value of Time (VoT) of the carpool passengers is higher than the VoT of the carpool driver and the latter is higher than that of the single driver. Pertaining to the carpool rider, the value of walk time is 16% higher compared to the in-vehicle VoT. A contextual preference for car-pooling was associated with work as trip purpose.

With respect to Greece, an SP experiment took place in Thessaloniki, two decades ago, in the framework of the EU 4th FP ICARO project, (ICARO, 1999; Papaioannou et al, 2001). The survey goal was to determine the percentage of persons willing to carpool under specific circumstances from home to work during the morning peak. The survey covered a specific area as home origins and the city centre as work destinations. Attributes in the SP games included the total journey time by car with and without the existence and use of an HOV lane by car poolers, the trip cost and the occupancy rate. A fractional factorial design of 9 combinations was employed instead of the full SP design of 27 combinations. Trip time and cost values were taken as % of the then average figures. Surveyed persons had to make a choice between a hypothetical option and the revealed one (paired choice). VoT figures for carpool drivers and riders were obtained, showing that there is a ratio of 1.56 between these two categories. Survey findings indicated that 5% of those asked are willing to car-pool as riders for a 17 min. journey (3.5 km) provided that they would save 60% of their initial trip cost and they would also reduce their journey time by 25%. Parking search time savings were not explicitly mentioned but they were taken as part of the overall journey time.

4. Study area and background information

The study area selected for this research is the catchment zone of the 20-km long air-rail corridor between “Doukissis Plakentias” and Athens Airport rail stations along "Attiki Odos" tolled motorway. This area comprises territories of five (5) municipalities with low population densities compared to the core centre of the Athens municipality (Table 4-1).

Table 4-1: Demographic and travel demand features of municipalities represented in study area

Municipality	Total Area (km ²)	Population	Population density (inh/km ²)	24h Travel Demand	PT Share (%)
Athens	39.0	664,046	17,026.8	1,491,531	78
Vrilissia	3.9	30,741	7,882.3	64,142	32
Penteli	36.1	34,934	967.7	27,051	27
Pallini	29.4	54,415	1,850.9	66,088	30
Paiania	53.2	26,668	501.3	28,833	27
Koropi	102.0	30,307	297.1	57,712	26

Source: ELSTAT & ATTIKO METRO

Table 4-2: Rail service level in the selected intermodal hubs

Metro/Suburban Rail Station	Morning Peak Headway (min)			Span of service		Morning Peak Boardings	
	MT	Sub	Comb ined	Metro	Suburban	Initial	Transfer
Doukissis Plakentias (DP)	5	20	4	05:30-24:00 (02:00) ^a	06:00-23:00	2,009	692
Koropi (KR)	30	20	12	06:30-23:30	06:00-23:00	91	287

^aFridays and Saturdays

Source: OASA & STASY

Travel in the selected corridor is normally during typical workdays faster when using urban rail to reach a central destination than using the car because of the congestion along the radial arterials. The PT share of Athens’ trip attractions (Table 4-1) is evidence in this respect.

Figure 4-1: Athens Metro Network and Intermodal Hubs (in yellow)

Table 4-3 presents the bus lines serving as feeder routes the two intermodal hubs of Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi. Boarding figures for morning period and 24 hours are also provided. Nights and weekends seem to be very suitable periods for dynamic ridesharing as a feeder mode to the (sub)urban rail featuring a high service level. The net effect is a higher rail utilization in low traffic periods through an otherwise suppressed demand.

Table 4-3: Bus feeder services and boardings recorded in the selected intermodal hubs

Metro/ Suburban Rail Station	Bus Line	MP Headway (min)	Span of Service	Destination	Boardings	
					MP	24h
Doukissis Plakentias	301	45	05:00- 23:00	Pallini- Penteli	109	1,298
	301B					
	302	35	05:00- 23:45	Pallini	364	4,333
	306	35	05:30- 22:30	Pallini	372	4,429
	307	40	06:15- 23:30	Pallini- Paiania	287	3,417
	314	25	06:30-23:05	D. Plakentias Station-Rafina		
	319	15	06:00-22:05	D. Plakentias Station-Spata		
	405	35	06:05- 23:30	Chalandri-Lelissia	260	3,095
	406	15	06:00-22:05	Pefkasia-Nosmitokopio		
	407	15	06:00-22:05	D. Plakentias Station-Nomismatikopio		
	411	30	06:00-22:55	P. Plakentias-Sismanogleio-Chalandri		
	447	30	05:25- 23:00	Chalandri-Vrilissia	176	2,095
	450	15	06:05- 23:30	Chalandri St. – N. Penteli		
451	30	05:30- 22:45	Chalandri- Penteli	371	4,417	
Koropi	120	60	5:25 – 20:25	Glyfada – Koropi Station		
	307	30	05:40-23:30	D. Plakentias St. – Koropi St.		
	308	15	05:35-23:40	Nomismatokopio - Koropi		
	309	30	05:00- 23:30	Koropi -Koropi Station	321	3,821
	330	45	06:00- 21:30	Koropi	319	3,798

Source: OASA & STASY

Both stations are equipped with P&R facilities which could encourage carpooling for multimodal travellers. Table 4-4 shows the main features of the park facilities. The utilization rate in DP's P&R station, is low to middle due to parking charges imposed. At DP hub, the P&R operator leases the land from the Metro's owner (ATTIKO METRO). Average parking duration is in the range of 6-8 hours. There is no strict parking enforcement in the area, thus resulting to intense parking spillover and lower parking demand at the facility. Parking availability is typically quite good. At KR station, the parking lot is saturated every workday during morning peak period. Furthermore, spillover parking of about 300 additional cars is noticed on a regular basis.

Table 4-4: P&R facilities features in the selected intermodal hubs

Metro/Suburban Rail Station	Area (m²)	Capacity	Fees per hour
Doukissis Plakentias (DP)	15,200-paved	630 spaces	0.5€ (up to 12hours per day)
Koropi (KR)	6,100-unpaved	300 spaces	Free

Source: Consultants own data

5. Survey Design

5.1. Methods and Instruments

According to the Terms of Reference of this contract, the survey method selected for reaching the project goals is a combined Revealed and Stated Preference Survey. The revealed preference (RP) part of the survey aims at gathering the trip characteristics of the persons to be approached. The Stated Preference part (SP) aims at acquiring the preferences and reactions of the interviewed with respect to alternative travel options that include carpooling as driver or rider as opposed to the current travel option. Trip makers of interest are those who live in the five Municipalities of Eastern Attica (mentioned in Table 4-1) and travel regularly to Athens Municipality or other area within the Attica basin using the Metro and/or the Suburban Rail and the two specific stations of Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi to board on them.

These travellers make a trip from home to their destination (work or other) and vice versa, consisting normally of three trip segments as follows (see Figure 5-2):

- a) First segment from home to Metro/Suburban rail station (Doukissis Plakentias or Koropi)
- b) Second segment from Metro/Suburban rail station to another Metro/Suburban rail station using Metro or suburban rail or a combination of these including the ISAP rail line
- c) Last segment from Metro/Suburban rail station where they get off the system to their final destination by any transport mode or on foot.

The reverse sequence applies to the return-home trip.

In this respect what is of interest is the first segment (first mile) of the home-based trip and the last segment of the return home trip (last mile).

Trip makers with respect to first/last mile can be classified in the following categories (strata):

1. Travellers who use PT bus
2. Travellers who drive alone (solo drivers) to/from any of the two stations
3. Travellers who drive with one or more co-riders to/from any of the two stations
4. Travellers who take taxi to/from any of the two stations
5. Travellers who are riders – not drivers- of another car travelling to/from any of the two stations

The last category is not of interest in the specific survey given that these specific travellers have nothing to benefit from becoming carpoolers either as drivers or as riders.

The first four categories (strata) may expect benefits in terms either of travel time savings, travel cost reductions, comfort and convenience or combination of all these.

It is clarified once more that travellers making a business trip or using a car, financially supported by their employer, are not considered for carpool travel options. Only commuters or trip makers travelling for personal reasons are examined.

To obtain the necessary data about the whole trip – outward and inward – and about the first and last mile of these trips a screening phase becomes necessary, so that each person to be interviewed is assigned to the right category. Then, the respective questions are asked in the RP part of the survey and the appropriate games and attribute levels/values are selected for the SP part.

The screening phase must be performed on the field and should be related to the two metro/suburban rail stations. It must be very short in duration, preferably less than 3-4 minutes, otherwise there is a risk of an incomplete – and non-usable - questionnaire. Travellers, especially in the morning peak periods are in a hurry and cannot tolerate delays due to lengthy surveys or other external unexpected interventions. In most cases their available time budget is the waiting time at the rail platform or at the bus berth. Alternatively, this screening phase may take place on the bus travelling towards the metro/suburban rail station or on the metro/suburban rail vehicles after boarding to them. For car drivers and riders, there is the option of approaching them at the park facility. This is perhaps the best method to identify those specific categories.

In brief, the following different field locations for the first survey phase can be distinguished:

- Metro/Suburban Railway Station Platform
- Ticket Purchasing Place inside the Station
- Parking Spaces
- Station Adjacent Roads
- Inside a Train passed the Doukissis Plakentias or the Koropi Metro/Suburban Rail Station
- Inside a Bus travelling towards the Metro/Suburban Rail Station

Filling the RP and SP parts of the questionnaire on the other hand requires longer time duration approaching 15 or even 20 min. This task cannot be accomplished on the field; rather it should be performed at a later time when the person approached is at home or at work, or elsewhere, with no time pressure. Completing the RP and SP parts requires focus and nuisance free environment.

Due to the above issues, the survey is designed to be executed for each eligible person in the sample in two Phases. The **first phase** is the screening phase which is completed on the field and the **second phase** is the full RP and SP survey which is completed at a later time - 2 to 14 days after the screening phase – at a location chosen by each interviewed person. An appointment between the interviewers and the interviewed is always possible to fill the questionnaire of the second phase. In fact, this option allows for answering and clarifying potential questions from the side of the interviewed.

Figure 5-1: Breakdown of home-based outward trips to different segments including walking and waiting times

The survey technique used in the first phase is the **Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI)**. Each interviewer carried a tablet or laptop loaded with an application specifically developed in the Lime Survey© Platform environment. Limesurvey© is a platform/software allowing professionals to develop customised surveys. Collected survey data were automatically stored in data bases designed every time for the sought purposes, so that data processing and analysis is fast and easy.

Each completed questionnaire in the first phase was assigned a unique alphanumeric code which was used for associating the second phase with the first one and at the same time served as password key for entering the Limesurvey© questionnaire of the second phase.

The survey technique for the questionnaire at the second phase was one of the following:

1. **Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI)** in case the interviewed enters the application from his/her computer, or
2. **Computer Assisted Telephone Survey (CATI)** in case the interviewer completes the questionnaire through telephone, asking the questions through telephone; the interviewed person should be able to open the application and view the SP game cards, or
3. **Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI)** in case the interviewer completes the questionnaire having arranged a meeting with the interviewed person.

In fact the third one was not used, since all respondents selected one of the first two.

5.2. Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire is structured in 5 sections as follows:

First Phase

Section A: General Information and data completed by the interviewer before starting the screening phase questions to the interviewed person

Section B: Screening questions to check whether the person is eligible for the RP/SP survey and assign him/her to the right category (stratum)

Second Phase

Section C: Revealed Preference Questionnaire. It applies to both inward and outward most common commuting or personal trips of the person interviewed. Depending on the category (stratum) a trip maker falls in, the respective sequence of questions appears. For example, for bus users for the trip segment home to station, questions about bus route, bus stop used, etc are made. For car drivers, parking search time and parking cost are requested, etc.

Section D: Socioeconomic characteristics of the person and the household he/she belongs to.

Section E: Stated Preference Questionnaire. It includes 8 game cards with three travel options every time with different attribute levels. Attribute figures for each level relate to the travel cost and travel time values corresponding to the person's responses in Section C. The total number of game cards used are 24 which are grouped in three octaves (see also SP Design Section).

Appendix A includes the successive screens of the application for both the first phase (screening phase) and the second phase.

A short introduction about the aim of the survey and what is expected is positioned in the beginning of Section A and Section C. Similarly a short explanatory note is placed in the beginning of Section E, i.e. the SP part of the questionnaire.

Special emphasis was given on the Data Protection rights of the persons who participated in the survey, both first and second phase. Interviewed persons had to explicitly consent to their participation in the survey. A text detailing in what they consent as well as their rights according to the EU and national legislation was given to them which they had to sign. (see also Chapter 7 in this report)

It is clarified that the survey was **anonymous**. No data such as name, address, religion, ethnicity, race, or other personal and sensitive data were requested or recorded. The unique alphanumeric code for accessing the application through internet was de-associated with the filled questionnaire two weeks after the completion of the second phase of the survey.

5.3. Sampling Method & Sampling Size

The population sampled comprises intermodal hub users at the two stations who make the first/last part of their journey by one of the following modes:

- CAT 1: Public Transport Feeder bus, falling in one of the bus lines of Table 4-3
- CAT 2: Driving Alone (SOV) and parking at or outside the designated P&R facility
- CAT 3: Driving with one or more passengers (HOV) and parking at or outside the designated P&R facility
- CAT 4: Taxi from home to Metro/suburban rail station and vice versa.

Trip makers who are dropped off/picked up by a family member or friend were not included in the targeted sample, since the alternative travel options are deemed inferior to the current ones. In other words, these trip makers are most likely non traders between trip attributes (time, cost, comfort, etc.).

Target respondents are people above the age of 18. As already mentioned, the respondents' population is categorised into two main groups according to their main trip purpose, namely commuting and other purpose. Business trips were not considered. The sampling procedure does not include by design car drivers being in need of their car during the day. Users of company cars were excluded from the survey. It is assumed that car trips shorter than 2 kms (i.e. about 5 minutes) are not worth of the carpool coordination effort.

According to the ATTIKO METRO transportation model developed in the Metro Development Study, approximately 39% of the road-side travellers' access/egress the two intermodal hubs of DP and KR by bus feeder and 61% by car/taxi. However, it was expected that the population of respondents will access or egress to a higher percentage by car. Pertaining to the existing users of bus feeder lines, the intention has is to promote the carpool alternative when the bus service is either not available (night) or very thin (weekend). Especially for aged persons (being at risk of social isolation) or persons without driver's license in low density areas, carpooling is a value alternative.

Given that the survey includes two phases, namely the first screening phase and the second RP & SP survey phase, the critical sample size figures are those of the second phase. As expected, the sample size of the first phase was much larger than the one of the second phase. The sample size depends on the following:

- a) Whether the approached persons satisfy the eligibility criteria for participation in the survey, i.e. whether they fall or not in one of the four eligible categories, CAT 1 to CAT 4.
- b) The response rate of those who satisfy the eligibility criteria, i.e. percentage of persons accepting to take part in the survey from the eligible ones.
- c) The percentage of those who though satisfy the eligibility criteria and accepted to take part in the second phase of the survey, finally change their mind and do not fill the RP and SP parts of the survey.

For determining the required sample size for the second phase of the survey, the choice-based sampling method was followed. A minimum sample size to be reached for each stratum in the population to ensure reliable findings was initially set. By combining the different current travel modes for the first/last part of the inward or outward trip and the trip purpose (commuting, other) we ended up with 8 different groups (4 strata * 2 trip purposes).

A minimum number of 35-40 valid questionnaires per group were deemed adequate for the research purposes. This threshold strongly depends on the number of game cards to be presented to each interviewee. Considering that 8 choice games with alternative travel options were shown to each interviewee, 320 observations per group of 40 persons can be reached. It is expected, based on past experience and similar surveys, that 10%-20% of completed questionnaires may be at the end unusable due to bias in the responses or other flaws. For this reason, the target sample size is increased by 25% for each group, so that the size of the usable questionnaires per group does not fall below 40.

Table 5-1 shows the groups to be surveyed and the indicative/targeted sample size for each hub location and trip purpose. The targeted sample for other purposes is slightly higher than the one for commuting, to account for wider variation.

Table 5-1: Sample size per population group, intermodal hub location and trip purpose

Intermodal Hub	Doukissis Plakentias				Koropi				Total	
	Travel Mode	PT bus	Car		Taxi	PT bus	Car			Taxi
			SOV driver	HOV driver			SOV driver	HOV driver		
Trip Purpose										
Commuting	40	40	40	40	30	30	30	30	280	
Other	45	45	45	45	35	35	35	35	320	
Total questionnaires	85	85	85	85	65	65	65	65	600	
Expected valid questionnaires	70	70	70	70	50	50	50	50	480	

For the screening phase it was expected that at least **1500** to **2000** persons in total would have to be approached on the field, in order to secure the figures of Table 5-1 per group and per station. An approximate figure of the exact ratio of persons accepting to participate over the persons approached was determined only after the end of the pilot survey (see Section 6.1 of the report) and the first days of the main survey.

5.4. Stated Preference Experimental Design

The State Preference Survey aims at gathering the responses of the interviewed persons with respect to their willingness to alter their usual travel behaviour and choose a different travel option. More specifically the new travel options offered to all eligible travellers who commute or travel for a personal reason include travelling as a carpool driver or as a carpool rider.

Overall, the travel options considered in the SP survey were four:

- PT Bus (PTB),
- Drive Alone (SOV),
- Drive with other passengers (HOV)
- Taxi Rider (TAR) or
- Carpool driver (CPD) or
- Carpool rider (CPR).

The travel option riding a car as passenger was not examined. The travel options were appearing as triplets on the game cards, meaning that the respondent had to choose one option among the current one and the alternative options, each time a game card was presented to him. The following travel choice sets shown in Table 5-2 were investigated.

Table 5-2: Travel Choice Sets to be examined

	Travel Option 1 (actual)	Travel Option 2	Travel Option 3
Choice Set 1	PT Feeder Bus	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 2	Car Driver (SOV)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 3	Car Driver (HOV)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider
Choice Set 4	Taxi Rider (TAR)	Carpool Driver	Carpool Rider

* Conditions to be met: licence holder and car available and work purpose

The RP part of the questionnaire reports values on current trip characteristics to the intermodal hubs, as well as socioeconomic features of travellers (e.g. car ownership level, number of driver licenses, PT travelcard holding, distance home - bus stop, employment status, work time flexibility). A research hypothesis is that people in households with fewer cars than drivers are more prone for carpooling. Current values are used as seeds to calculate attribute values for the SP part of the questionnaire. Attitudinal responses rule out carpooling as alternative filter for non-traders.

The attributes presented in the PT (bus feeder) and SOV alternatives are constant among alternatives, i.e. variable attributes were presented only for the carpooling alternatives (driver, rider). Note that driving alone a car or using bus feeder is conditioned by car availability or PT service availability respectively. Carpooling depends not only on car availability but also on the willingness to share a car.

The initial attributes considered for the SP games were the following:

- Travel time, for all alternatives
- Travel cost, for all alternatives including parking cost for SOV, HOV, CPD and CPR
- Preferential Parking (Existence or non-existence), only for CPD and CPR
- Meeting Point (Home or Out of home) for CPR
- Flexible time schedule for CPD and CPR

- Guaranteed Rid Home (GRH) for CPR

After thorough consideration, it was decided to exclude the attribute Guaranteed Rid Home (GRH) for the Carpool Rider (CPR). The main reason is that the compensation required to be given to the CPR, in terms of paid taxi trip, or similar, should a change in the departure time of one of the two travellers occurs cannot be secured. This type of guarantee presumes that an agency, or the employer of the CPR, or the state, will be able to fund the cost for the GRH.

As a result, five attributes were selected to be included in the utility functions for the discrete choice models to be constructed along with the levels that formed the different values for the game cards. These, along with the way their levels are defined, are presented in Table 5-3. The levels were specified either in absolute terms or in percental terms. Three of the attributes receive three levels, coded as L, M, H and the remaining ones receive two levels coded as L and H. The first four alternatives refer to the current existing travel options as recorded by the RP survey. The other two refer to the travel options under investigation through the SP survey.

Travel time is specified as an alternative-specific attribute and the travel cost as a generic variable. Separate specifications are considered, referring to riders being household members or non-household members respectively. In the former case is expected that carpooling with household members is a utility for the driver, in the latter case a disutility.

Emphasis was posed on non-household members and unknowns who are the main focus group of the RIDE2RAIL app to be developed and tested as part of the RIDE2RAIL project in Athens. Equal sharing of parking cost as well as of fuel and toll cost is the typical case, especially with unknowns.

Based on these, the number of possible combinations in the SP game sets was calculated to $3^3 \cdot 2^1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 2^2 = 1,728$. This figure represents the full factorial SP design. A fractional factorial, facing satisfactorily the main effects, would result to 24 combinations, which are far too many to be negotiated by the interviewees. For this reason, it has been decided to split these 24 combinations into 3 blocks. Each block should be treated by 15 to 20 respondents (FSGV, 1996). A random selection special routine, developed in R software language (R Core Team, 2013), returned the 3*8 combinations.

Table 5-3: Trip Attributes and Attribute Levels for current and carpooling travel options

Alternative (Travel Option)	Attribute	Reference Source/Value	Variations		
			L	M	H
PT Bus (PTB)	Travel Cost (ticket)	0 €		#	
	Travel Time (WLT + IVT + WLK + WAT ^a)	TM ^c or OASA		#	
Drive Alone (SOV)	Car Travel cost (fuel + parking)	TM ^c		#	
	Travel Time (IVT + PST)	Formula + RP ^b		#	
Drive not alone (HOV)	Travel Cost (fuel + parking)	RP ^b		#	
	Travel Time (WAT + IVT + WLK + WAT ^a)	Formula		#	
Taxi rider (TAR)	Taxi Cost	RP ^b		#	
	Travel Time (IVT + WLK + WAT ^a)	Formula		#	
Carpool Driver (CPD)	Travel cost (fuel + parking)	½ SOV or HOV travel cost +1/4 parking cost	-25%	#	+25%
	Travel Time (IVT + DTT + PST)	TTT + 2-4 min	#	+2	+4
	Preferential Parking	-	Yes	-	No
	Flexible Schedule (1h, 3h, 12h)	-	12 h	3h	1h
Carpool Rider (CPR)	Travel cost (fuel + parking)	½ SOV or HOV travel cost +1/4 parking cost	-25%	#	+25%
	Travel Time (WAT + IVT + WLK + PST)	TTT + 2 – 4 min	#	+2	+4
	Meeting Point (home, Out of home)	-	HM	-	OHM
	Flexible Schedule (1h, 3h, 12h)	-	12h	3h	1h

denotes reference value. For current travel options it is obtained either from available data or from RP survey; for carpool options it is calculated as shown in the respective cells

^a Different for each Intermodal hub

^b Respondent specific

^c TM: ATTIKO METRO (AM) Transportation Model

WLT: Walking Time

PST: Parking Search Time

TTT: (Total) Travel Time

IVT: In Vehicle Time

DTT: Detour Travel Time

WAT: Wait Time

The reference value for each attribute per travel option is as follows:

- For the current option is the one obtained from the RP survey or from the AM transportation model (e.g. travel time between a location and the intermodal hubs, travel distance, travel cost based on distance, parking cost, etc.) or from OASA available data
- For carpool travel options it is calculated by taking into account the initial reference values as previously described and then by properly adjusting for the new conditions. For instance, for the 'carpooling driver' option, the travel cost obtained from the survey is increased to account for any detour required to pick up the carpool rider and then is divided by two, since the total travel cost is equally split among the travellers. An assumption is made that most carpools include two riders only. Similarly, the reference travel time for this option is increased by the detour extra time for the driver and the walk plus the wait time for the rider.

Table 5-4 below presents the 8 combinations per block for the carpool driver and carpool rider travel options.

Table 5-4: Trip Attributes and Attribute Levels for current and carpooling travel options

BLOCK 1

CPD Attributes				CPR Attributes			
a1	a2	a3	a4	a1	a2	a3	a4
H	L	L	M	H	H	L	L
H	M	H	H	M	H	H	M
H	M	H	H	H	L	L	H
H	H	H	M	M	H	L	H
H	M	L	H	M	H	L	H
L	M	L	H	H	L	L	M
L	L	L	L	M	L	L	M
L	L	H	M	M	H	L	M

BLOCK 2

CPD Attributes				CPR Attributes			
a1	a2	a3	a4	a1	a2	a3	a4
H	M	H	L	H	L	L	L
M	M	H	H	M	H	L	M
L	M	L	M	M	L	H	M
L	L	H	M	H	L	L	M
M	M	H	L	H	L	H	M
M	L	H	M	H	H	L	H
H	M	H	L	H	L	H	L
M	L	H	M	H	L	H	M

BLOCK 3

CPD Attributes				CPR Attributes			
a1	a2	a3	a4	a1	a2	a3	a4
M	L	H	L	H	H	L	L
H	L	H	L	M	L	L	L
M	M	H	H	M	H	H	L
L	H	H	L	M	L	H	H
H	M	L	H	M	L	H	L
H	M	H	M	H	L	H	M
H	M	L	H	M	L	L	H
H	M	H	H	M	L	L	H

Attributes a1 to a4 for the Carpool Driver (CPD) are as follows:

- a1. Travel Cost (operating cost + parking cost)
- a2. Travel Time (IVT + DTT + PST)
- a3. Preferential Parking
- a4. Flexible Schedule (1h, 3h, 12h)

Attributes a1 to a4 for the Carpool Rider (CPR) are as follows:

- a1. Travel Cost (operating cost + parking cost)
- a2. Travel Time (WAT + IVT + WLK + PST)
- a3. Meeting Point
- a4. Flexible Schedule (1h, 3h, 12h)

The Formulas and the values per attribute used for each travel option and category of respondent are presented in Tables A1 to A4 in Appendix B of this report

6. Survey Execution

The Survey execution comprises 3 parts:

- Pilot Survey
- Main Surveys
- Supplementary Surveys

6.1 Pilot Survey

A pilot survey which was part of the overall survey planning has been specified in the Terms of Reference. The pilot helped standardizing the survey instrument and tested the complexity of choice situations. It also gave an indication what the response rates had been in the screening phase of the survey.

The pilot phase took place at both stations. The targeted number of completed questionnaires during the pilot was 40 questionnaires for the four categories, ideally equally allocated. Persons approached were representative as possible of the population to be sampled, meaning that different trip purposes, different gender and age groups and different socioeconomic characteristics had to be covered.

No changes in the questionnaire were required as a result of the pilot survey. The initial design was proved quite satisfactory. Some textual only improvements took place in a couple of questions. The pilot phase also provided useful information about the survey execution, such as required time to complete the first and the second phase, good practices in approaching the persons to be interviewed, preferred locations in each station for the survey, communication problems with the survey team, etc.

Finally, it provided the necessary information and knowledge about the reactions from the potential respondents side with respect to their understanding of the Data Protection Legislation and their rights.

6.2 Main Survey Execution

The main survey was conducted at Doukissis Plakentias (DP) and Koropi (KR) stations. The duration of the survey was 8 working days, and the implementation took place during morning and evening peaks, namely between 7:00-11:00 and 15:00-19:00. More specifically, the main survey took place the following dates:

- Wednesday 29th June
- Thursday 30th June
- Friday 1st July
- Monday 4th July
- Tuesday 5th July
- Wednesday 6th July
- Thursday 7th July
- Friday 8th July

The interviewers approached possible responders inside or around the two stations, trying to involve a representative sample of the population. They also followed the instructions that are presented in the Planning report.

Before the filling of the questionnaire, and given that the survey process had been clearly explained by the interviewers, each responder had to declare their consent to participate in the survey. In

addition, the interviewers clarified to the responders that the survey is anonymous, and that there will not be any association between any personal data and their responses. Finally, the interviewers informed the responders regarding their rights based on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as well as whom they would contact in order to declare complaints or raise a grievance.

The interviewers followed the Computer Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) survey technique, filling up sections A and B of the questionnaire in the LimeSurvey© Platform environment in their tablets. In case the approached people fell in one of the four under consideration categories, and were also willing to participate to the second phase of the survey, they were provided with a card that indicates their personal responder code, a link that directs them to the Internet site that contains the sections C, D, and E of the questionnaire, as well as contact details of POLINDE Consulting Engineers (see Annex).

Moreover, after having completed the first phase, a percentage of approximately 5% of the responders were chosen in order to participate in a validation process. More specifically, in each station the supervisors asked the chosen responders to answer again to the questions of the first phase, in order to validate that the responders had answered with honesty to the interviewers.

During the first phase, **4246** trip makers were approached, of whom **1830** were eligible for the survey. Of the aforementioned 1830 eligible participants, **1209** agreed to proceed to the remote questionnaire (second phase), either by signing the consent form or by just accepting to take an interview card (see Annex). Finally, of the 1209 that agreed to proceed to the second phase of the questionnaire, only **414** completed it. The completed questionnaires involve:

- 189 Trip makers that travel by their passenger car.
- 120 Trip makers who used public bus.
- 62 Trip makers that travel by their passenger car together with other riders.
- 43 Trip makers that use a Taxi.

It should be pointed out that the trips makers that accessed the online survey were **494**. However, only **414** of them fully completed it (85 trips makers accessed the electronic form of the questionnaire without fully completing it).

6.3 Supplementary Surveys

Two Supplementary Survey took place in order to increase the number of responses in specific categories. The first supplementary survey in late July targeted only responses by the category Drivers with Passenger and took place at Doukissis Plakentias station only the following days and during non-peak period (9:00am-15:00pm):

- Wednesday 27th July
- Thursday 28th July
- Friday 29th July

The second supplementary survey took place in both stations (Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi) and targeted all categories in order to increase the total number of valid questionnaires and reach a target sample over 480 in total. The dates of the second supplementary survey are as follows:

- Monday 5th September
- Tuesday 6th September
- Wednesday 7th September

6.4 Overall Results of the Surveys

After the execution of the pilot surveys, the main surveys and the two supplementary surveys a total number of 493 completed questionnaires was achieved. The time gap between the last survey day on the field (7th of September) and the on-line completion date was one week. In fact, the on-line access for the responders was interrupted on the 15th of September. The 493 completed questionnaires involve:

- 227 Trip makers who travel alone towards the Metro/Suburban rail station.
- 143 Trip makers who use public bus.
- 79 Trip makers who travel by their passenger car together with other riders.
- 44 Trip makers who use a Taxi to reach the station.

In total and referring to all surveys (pilot, main, supplementary) more than 5400 people were approached, a number that is more than twice the number that was initially envisaged (the initial estimate was to approach 1500-2000 responders).

In addition to the above, it should also be mentioned that this survey has targeted successfully 151 suitable users who, having completed the SP questionnaire, also gave their consent and email addresses to be contacted and informed by Attiko Metro S.A. for their potential participation in the Athens demo of RIDE2RAIL project (see Appendix A, Fig.A-28). These email addresses have been sent to Attiko Metro S.A. for further communication, relevant to RIDE2RAIL demo, with these users.

6.5 Problems encountered and Solutions

During the execution of the project, several difficulties were evident. Firstly, the pilot survey started on the 20th of June instead of the 29th of April. This 7-week delay is totally reasoned, since the approval of the questionnaire by ATTIKO METRO S.A. took much longer than it was initially anticipated. As a result of the issues (discussed in section 4.1), the approval of the questionnaire by ATTIKO METRO S.A. took place on Wednesday 8th of June, and at the subsequent day, 9th of June, the legal representative of POLINDE EE signed the GDPR form of ATTIKO METRO S.A.. The signing of the GDPR form was a pre-condition for the execution of the pilot survey.

One week of delay, between Monday 13th of June, which was the earliest date that the pilot survey could have started, and 20th of June, which is the actual date that pilot has started, was caused to the fact that on Friday 10th of June ATTIKO METRO S.A. requested the signature of each interviewee on the tablet, instead of just a consent tick on the tablet, as was indicated by POLINDE representatives. However, the application of LimeSurvey does not provide this technical feature of digital signature. As a result, after discussions with ATTIKO METRO S.A. a paper form was created to be handed out to the interviewees, in order to sign it up.

The approval of the questionnaire took much longer than initially anticipated due to:

- a) The high technical complexity of the questionnaire: Several meetings and constant communication with the representatives of ATTIKO METRO were required.
- b) The demand for compliance with the GDPR issues, stated by the ATTIKO METRO S.A. (the issues regarding GDPR will be analysed thoroughly in the next chapter)

During the completion of the main survey, an additional problem was identified and was the low number of trip makers falling into two specific categories.

- Trip makers who travel by their passenger car together with other riders.
- Trip makers who use a Taxi.

An initial measure to cover the time schedule discrepancy was that the pilot survey was concluded in 1 week, instead of 2 weeks envisaged in the initial time-schedule. Moreover, the main survey was executed in only 2 weeks (including the organization of the activity), instead of at least 3 weeks.

The team of POLINDE EE have worked repeatedly during weekends to launch the survey as soon as possible. Additional human resources were positioned to the project to speed up the preparation of both surveys (e.g., graphic designer involved to produce more appealing questionnaires to the users, a resource that was not initially envisaged as a need for the implementation of the project).

Moreover, the questionnaire was well designed and as a result no modifications were needed for the main survey, which would have required additional time.

In terms of low number of responses for the Taxi Trip makers, the interviewers spend enormous part of the main survey to areas where taxi disembark and embark passengers and this has a result to get much fewer completed questionnaire for the dedicated time intervals of the main survey as initially envisaged.

For car drivers with other riders, a supplementary survey of three days was carried out targeting only this category and this has added further delays to the completion of the survey.

Despite these actions, the number of trips makers from these categories is still low. It should be mentioned though that especially for Koropi station, it is extremely rare to locate trip makers who approach the station by taxi. Furthermore, a large number of trip makers with co-drivers in this station use corporate vehicle (large number of large corporations in the area) and they are not considered by the criteria of the R&D programme eligible as responders.

7. Data Protection Issues

As mentioned above, the delays in the execution of the survey are highly attributed to limitations arisen by the implementation of General Data Protection Regulation. The General Data Protection Regulation, or GDPR, is the well-known EU law that came into effect in May 2018 with the purpose to create a uniform standard of data protection law in the European Union. It lays down the rules for the protection of natural persons and their right to privacy with regard to the processing and free movement of personal data. GDPR compliance entails respecting user privacy and anonymity. In total, the GDPR empowers EU citizens with eight individual rights, including the right not to have one's personal data collected and processed without prior consent.

In summary, special emphasis was put on Data Protection rights of the persons who would participate in the survey, both during the first and the second phase. Interviewed persons had to explicitly consent to their participation in the survey. A text detailing in what they consent, as well as their rights according to the EU and national legislation was given to them, which they had to sign. The text in Greek is presented in Appendix C It was clarified to all persons approached that the survey is **anonymous**. No data such as name, address, religion, ethnicity, race, or other personal and sensitive data were requested or recorded. Finally, the unique alphanumeric code for accessing the application through internet will be de-associated with the filled questionnaire two weeks after the completion of the second phase of the survey.

Having these in mind, ATTIKO METRO has established strict internal procedures in order to comply with the GDPR regulations.

The complications with the GDPR are divided in two categories:

1. To those related to the development of the questionnaire
2. To those related to the execution of survey

The development of questionnaire took much longer than anticipated in order to comply totally with the GDPR. A thorough review of all questions and several meetings with ATTIKO METRO S.A. were carried out in order to eliminate any interference with GDPR. Indicative examples of changes in the development are:

- The interviewers do not mark on the map their residence or working place but a close intersection.
- The question to determine the number of non-adults members of the households was abolished
- The preface of the questionnaire was written in such way to not have any interference with GDPR.

Regarding the execution of the survey, the most difficult issue was related to the fact that the interviewers had to sign at the end of the first part of the questionnaire in order to consent but the Lime survey platform did not provide such feature and clicking on a box was not approved as adequate by the ATTIKO METRO Data Protection Officer. To overcome such issue, hard copy statements were also developed and given to interviewers to be signed for consent forcing some potential respondents to abandon the survey due to time restrictions (limitations).

Additionally, it was very difficult to reach the required number of 600 fully completed questionnaires since the responder has to complete the Phase B on his own on his own device according to the requirements of GDPR and the interviewer can only assist/guide him by the phone.

8. Data Cleaning, Checking and Processing

8.1 Data Cleaning and Checking

Data obtained either during the first phase of the questionnaire survey or during the second phase were examined and checked in various stages of the overall process so that the data set to be used for analysis is clean from various errors and/or mistakes and is flawless.

The following checks and subsequently actions were taken during the first phase:

- Checking that the interview unique code corresponds to the questionnaire completion date.
- Checking that the interview unique code corresponds to the respective Metro/Suburban Rail station.
- Checking that the initial trip origin and the final trip destination of a trip are different.
- Checking that the interview code is in fact unique and correct.

With respect to the second phase of the survey, the following checks were made:

- Checking that the questionnaire has been fully completed (some fields, such as the household income level do not need to be answered in order to consider the questionnaire complete).
- Checking that the interview unique code corresponds to the first phase code assigned by the interviewees.
- Checking that the initial trip origin and the final trip destination of the trip are different (so it is not a circular trip)
- Checking that the Municipalities declared for home and work locations correspond to the locations indicated on the digital map shown to the interviewed persons
- Checking that the category in which a person falls in (e.g. bus user for the trip segment home to station) is identical in both interview phases.

Based on the above and after the necessary corrections, where applicable, 3.5% of all questionnaires were not included in the first phase data set since the majority of responders did not wish to participate in the survey. Regarding the second phase approximately 20% of the questionnaires were removed due to the fact that the respondents did not consent to the GDPR declaration form or they did not fill completely the questionnaire.

Once all the above checks were completed, all data were exported to XLS and Data base formats. Additional logical checks were made which include the following:

- Time to travel from home to Metro/Suburban rail station was checked to make sure that reflects real conditions.
- Time to travel from home to Metro/Suburban rail station was compared against the total travel time from home to final destination. The respective ratio was calculated. Records with ratio values exceeding a certain threshold depending on the trip characteristics were excluded from the data set.
- Checks of Parking Search Time (PST) for trip makers falling to CAT2 and against the travel time from home to station. Records including PST values greater than travel time values from home to station were excluded.
- Travel cost derived from home to station distance for trip makers falling to CAT2 and CAT3 groups

As a result of these checks, 8 questionnaires were excluded from the data set. The final data set of the first and second phase – the latter being used for the MNL modelling tasks – are shown in Table 8-1.

Table 8-1: Questionnaire statistics

Step	Number of responses
Phase A	
Initial Sample	5,399
Screening based on Trip Purpose (business trips and trips with other purpose where excluded)	5,247
Screening based on Trip mode of Arrival (riders of private vehicles or users of other mode were excluded)	3,197
Screening based on Trip Frequency (rarely trip frequency was excluded)	2,855
Final Sample (based on the willingness to complete the rest of the questionnaire)	2,114
Phase B	
Initial Sample	493
Final sample (based on logical tests)	485

The 485 questionnaires remained for the modelling purposes translate into 3,880 records, since each interviewed person responded to 8 SP games, choosing a travel option among three alternatives, namely the current option, the option to travel as Carpool Driver (CPD) and the option to travel as Carpool Rider (CPR).

8.2 Athens Demo Side

As mentioned in the Introduction, one of the main goals of the survey has been to find an adequate number of metro users willing to take part in the Athens demo site of the RIDE2RAIL project satisfying the selection criteria specified by AM. The demo application was developed by the RIDE2RAIL consortium partners and consisted of two applications:

- a) the “Travel Companion” app which was addressed to persons who were not using a car to access to or depart from a Metro/Suburban rail station, and were willing to find suitable carpooling matches,
- b) the “Driver Companion” app which was addressed to persons who use their car to access to or depart from a Metro/Suburban rail station and look for a carpool travel companion.

From all the surveyed persons, 151 persons in total agreed to participate in the pilot applications of the R2R Athens demo. The incentives offered to users to participate in the Athens demo were a bonus check cashable at Supermarket shops and more specifically checks of 30 € for travellers and 50 € for drivers.

8.3 Data Processing

Final data sets were processed in order to obtain several useful statistics and other numerics regarding the trip characteristics of trip makers and in particular of those who chose to use a carpooling travel option either as Carpool Drivers (CPD) or Carpool Riders (CPR). Furthermore, data processing used to create some new variables to be tested in modelling travel behaviour of the people in the sample(s).

Table 8-2 presents the main sample statistics with respect to the two survey stations (Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi), the transport mode used to travel from home to station and the main trip purpose. It can be seen that some sub groups have a poor representation such as HOV drivers or taxi drivers travelling for other than commuting purposes. This is due to the fact that these travellers are very few in the trip makers' population.

Table 8-2: Final survey sample per population group, intermodal hub location and trip purpose

Intermodal Hub	Doukissis Plakentias				Koropi				Total
	PT bus	Car		Taxi	PT bus	Car		Taxi	
		SOV driver	HOV driver			SOV driver	HOV driver		
Trip Purpose									
Commuting	51	111	33	21	47	79	22	10	374
Other	28	19	8	5	16	11	16	8	111
Total valid questionnaires	79	130	41	26	63	90	38	18	485

All questions included in the survey, both first and second phase, were coded. New variables created were also coded. The notation of all variable code names are shown in Appendix D

9. Overview of Survey Statistics

The most important statistics for both first phase and second phase of the survey are presented in this chapter. The statistics refer to cleaned and checked data sets.

9.1 Phase A Main Descriptive Statistics

As mentioned earlier, the initial questionnaire sample was 5,399 respondents. 64.5% of the interviews was conducted at Doukissis Plakentias station while the other 35.5% was conducted at Koropi station. More than 95% of the questionnaires were conducted on the metro/suburban railway platforms of both stations.

More than 70% of the respondents hold a driving license, while almost 60% of the respondents have in their possession a private passenger vehicle. The persons in the sample holding an OASA PT card other than a single fare ticket represent 64.6%. From those, as shown in Figure 9-1, the majority have a monthly OASA card (79%), 5% an annual PT card and 13.1% have a rechargeable PT card.

Figure 9-1: Type of PT card

Survey participants were asked about their trip purpose and as shown in Figure 9-2 more than half percent are commuters, approximately 25% are travel for personal reasons and about 3% are travel for business and other purposes; the latter were excluded from the rest of the survey.

Figure 9-2: Trip purpose

Of those who continued the interview, almost all (98,1%) were about to board to metro or suburban rail. Regarding their trip mode of arrival to station, more than half of the sample arrived by bus or by car as drivers. Almost 4% of the sample arrived with taxi while 13.3% on foot. Trip mode of arrival to the station is presented in Figure 9-3.

Figure 9-3: Trip mode of arrival to station

Based on the screening process, respondents that arrived at the station with a private vehicle as passengers or with another mode not listed were excluded from the rest of the questionnaire.

For the majority of the respondents (84.6%) their trip origin is their home while trip destination for 54% of the respondents is their work location. Trip frequency of the examined trip is presented in Figure 9-4. As can be derived from the Figure, 57% of the sample performs this trip on a daily basis

while 25% at least once a week. 10.7% of the sample that stated “Rarely” as trip frequency of their journey were excluded from the following questions of the survey.

Figure 9-4: Trip frequency

The last questions of the questionnaire were about whether the respondents are internet users and whether they wish to complete the rest of the questionnaire, i.e., participate to Phase B of the survey. Almost 98% of the respondents stated that they use internet and 74% of the sample expressed a desire to continue to the next stage of the survey.

9.2 Phase B Main Descriptive Statistics

Phase B of the questionnaire survey is divided into three sections. The first section is about the revealed preference part of the survey where respondents revealed their current trip characteristics from home to metro/suburban rail stations. The second section is about their socioeconomic characteristics. The third and final section is about the stated preference part of the survey regarding the willingness to accept carpooling responding to hypothetical alternative travel options.

Revealed Preference Questionnaire

The Revealed Preference part of the survey aims at gathering the trip characteristics of the interviewees. It applies to both inward and outward most common commuting or personal trips of the person interviewed.

As presented in Figure 9-5, respondents use metro/suburban rail for trip with home origin mainly on a daily basis (67.2%), or 3-4 times a week (23.1%). In more than half of trips with home origin respondents board on metro/suburban on Doukissis Plakentias station.

Figure 9-5: Trip frequency of first mile home based trips continuing with metro/suburban rail

Subsequent questions of the survey are about trip with home origin to another destination using metro/suburban railway. More than 77.1% of the above trips are made for commuting while 11.5% of them are made for study purposes and 9.7% for personal reasons (Figure 9-6).

Figure 9-6: Trip purpose of first mile home based trips continuing with metro/suburban rail

Regarding the transport mode used during the first mile of their trips, almost 62% were made with a private vehicle, 45.4% from which as driver with no passengers (SOV) and 16.3% as a driver with passengers onboard (HOV). Bus used as a mode of transport by 29.3% of the sample and 9.1% of respondents used a taxi during the first mile of their trips.

Figure 9-7: Transport Mode of First Mile trips

With regard to the transport mode used by the respondents from the metro/suburban rail alighting station to their final destination, 68% continued their trip on foot while 18.4% continued by bus (Figure 9-8).

Figure 9-8: Transport Mode (Outward Egress)

The following questions of the survey are for the respondents (87.8%) who used metro/suburban rail when travelling back home. The greatest percentage (91.5%) of these trips were made with trip origin work or study location. Figure 9-9 presents the transport mode used by the respondents from origin to station during the return home trip. The highest number of trips 68.5% were made on foot and 17.5% by bus.

Figure 9-9: Transport Mode to station (Return Home)

More than 80% of the respondents used a metro line for their trip compared to a suburban line. Regarding the transport mode used during the last segment of their trips, almost 47% of the sample used their car with no passengers, 11.8% used their car with at least one passenger onboard and 20.1% travelled by bus.

Figure 9-10: Transport Mode (Last Mile)

Socioeconomic characteristics

With regard to socioeconomic characteristics of the sample, 58% are women while the age group to which the respondents belong is presented in Figure 9-11. Almost 52% of the sample belong to age group 36-55, 38% to age group 18-35 and 1% of the sample are over 65 years old.

Figure 9-11: Age group

Almost 70% of the sample work either to public or private sector as employees, 9.7% are freelancers and 13.4% are student.

Figure 9-12: Occupation

Concerning the economic status of the respondents, almost 20% state an average monthly household income up to 1000€, 43.8% state 1000-2000€ and 36.3% over 2000€.

Figure 9-13: Average monthly household income

More than half of the sample (57.8%) belongs to a household with 3 or 4 members, probably a family with 1 or 2 children while approximately 30% belong to a household with 1 or 2 members. More than 83% of the respondents, have 1 or 2 private vehicles in their household while only 6.5% of the sample belongs to a household with no access to a private vehicle. Almost 71% lives in a household with 1 or 2 members with driving license.

Just before the stated preference part of the questionnaire, participants were asked about the two most unfavourable criteria, in relation to their travel to the metro/suburban rail station by public transport. Figure 9-14 shows the responses of the interviewed regarding the factors they consider negative for using bus services in the areas around the stations of Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi.

Figure 9-14: PT Bus quality aspects marked as mostly disappointing

For the majority of respondents, the most important reason is low bus frequency, lack of timetable and emergency information and high bus occupancy while the least important reasons are lack of bus shelters.

Stated Preference Questionnaire

The State Preference part of the survey aims at gathering the responses of the interviewed persons with respect to their willingness to alter their usual travel behaviour and choose a different travel option, namely as Carpool Driver (CPD) or Carpool Rider (CPR).

At the beginning of this section, participants were asked whether they are aware about the concept of carpooling. Almost 80% of the sample were familiar with the term, while for those who were not aware of the subject, they were given a brief description about the concept of carpooling. More than 67% of the sample have a positive or very positive opinion about carpooling while only 7.6% have a negative or very negative opinion about the subject.

Figure 9-15: Personal opinion about carpooling

A series of game cards with different attribute levels were presented to survey participants with the aim to collect the preferences and reactions with respect to alternative travel options that include carpooling as driver or rider as opposed to the current travel option. In general, more than 57% of the sample selected carpooling as travel option either as a driver or rider.

Figure 9-16: Choice of users

Regarding, the choice of users in the alternative scenarios an analysis was made based on their personal characteristics and preferences. Figure 9-17 presents the choice of groups per user group according to the current transport mode used during the first mile of their trip. PT bus users, for different time and cost values, choose in a higher percentage their current transport mode compared to the alternative carpooling options. Taxi users prefer to a higher percentage carpooling as a rider, while SOV or HOV drivers prefer carpool as drivers.

Figure 9-17: Choice of users per group

With respect to the choices according to the gender, men choose at a greater degree carpool as drivers, while women carpool as riders as shown in Figure 9-17. The models developed per user

group according to transport mode used for the first mile trip indicate that the gender is not a significant attribute except for the case of bus users.

Figure 9-18: Choice of users per gender

Figure 9-18 shows that to a considerable degree, the older the respondents' age, the less likely to choose an alternative travel option compared to the current transport mode used. On the contrary, respondents falling in younger ages prefer to a higher percentage carpool as riders.

Figure 9-19: Choice of users per age group

With regard to the average monthly household income of respondents, it appears that there are not significant differences between the different income classes, with the exception of the category of 1000-1500€ where respondent in this category choose to a greater degree carpool as rider.

Figure 9-20: Choice of users per income level

9.3 Statistics of Main trip Characteristics

In this section main trip characteristics are presented both for the sample as a whole and for individual user categories based on the transport mode used during the first mile of their trips. Moreover, time and cost distributions for key trip parts are presented in the form of histograms.

For the first mile of respondents' trip, the following figures depict the time and cost distributions per user category. For bus users, the mean travel time from home to station is approximately 23 minutes. For SOV and HOV drivers the respective time consists of the travel time from home to station plus the Parking Search Time (PST). For SOV drivers, mean travel time is 17 minutes plus 4 minutes searching for parking while for HOV drivers is approximately 20 minutes and 5 minutes respectively. Travel time from home to station for taxi users is 15 minutes. In terms of cost variables, mean parking cost for SOV drivers is just 0.2 € while the mean cost of travelling by taxi is 5.8 €.

Figure 9-21: Travel Time Home-Platform First Mile for Bus

Figure 9-22: Travel Time Home-Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers

Figure 9-23: Parking Search Time Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers

Figure 9-24: Parking Cost Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers

Figure 9-25: Travel Time Home-Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers

Figure 9-26: Parking Search Time Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers

Figure 9-27: Travel Time Home-Terminal First Mile for Taxi

Figure 9-28: Taxi Cost First Mile

As presented in Figure 9-29, average waiting time on the station platform for all users is approximately 8 minutes.

Figure 9-29: Waiting platform time

In terms, of total travel time from origin to destination and total travel cost for all respondents, based on following Figures, mean total travel time is 60 minutes and mean total travel cost is 4€.

Figure 9-30: Travel Time Origin-Destination

Figure 9-31: Travel Cost Origin-Destination

10. Discrete Choice Model Development

10.1 Discrete Choice Modelling Basics

Discrete choice models are used to explain or predict a choice from a set of two or more discrete (i.e. distinct and separable; mutually exclusive) alternatives. For example, a discrete choice model may be used to analyse why people choose to drive, take the subway, or walk to work. Discrete choice models operate within a framework of rational choice; that is, it is assumed that when confronted with a discrete set of options, people choose the option of maximal benefit or utility. It follows from this assumption that utility of a choice is a function of the characteristics of the possible choices and the characteristics of the person making the choice. These models rely on the hypothesis that the decision maker is able to rank the different alternatives by an order of preference represented by a utility function. For a choice of an alternative i among a set of j alternatives, each alternative is therefore characterized by an utility value U_i and the alternative l is chosen if and only if $U_i > U_j$.

Two types of discrete choice data exist: (a) stated preference and (b) revealed preferences. Stated preference data is obtained from hypothetical scenarios or a set of choices presented by the investigator to the subjects, which was also the case in the present Stated Preference part of the questionnaire survey.

The study employs multinomial mixed logit models in order to examine a number of parameters that may have an effect on the choice made by the users with respect to their willingness to alter their usual travel behaviour and choose a different travel option. In general, when one tries to explain discrete choices, i.e. choices of one among multiple mutually exclusive alternatives, multinomial logit models are used. In this case, the mutually exclusive alternatives were the three travel options for the first or last mile of respondents' trip: current travel option, carpool as a driver and carpool as a rider. Model specifications selected were the ones providing the best fit to the experimental data when choosing among three possible travel option alternatives.

Multinomial logistic regression is used to predict categorical placement in or the probability of category membership on a dependent variable based on multiple independent variables. The independent variables can be either dichotomous (i.e., binary) or continuous (i.e., interval or ratio in scale). Multinomial logistic regression is a simple extension of binary logistic regression that allows for more than two categories of the dependent or outcome variable. Like binary logistic regression, multinomial logistic regression uses maximum likelihood estimation to evaluate the probability of categorical membership. With a sample of respondents, one can estimate the parameters of the logit model, i.e. the coefficients of time and price in the utility function and also any other useful variable that may affect respondent's choice. The individual must choose one alternative among J different and exclusive alternatives. A level of utility may be defined for each alternative and the individual is supposed to choose the alternative with the highest level of utility. It is important to understand that the utility and therefore, the choice is purely deterministic from the decision maker's point of view. The fitted model can then be used to predict the impact of some changes of the explanatory variables on the market shares of travel options.

In this research study, an extension of multinomial logit models was used, namely mixed logit models. A mixed logit model or random parameters logit model is a logit model for which the parameters are assumed to vary from one individual to another. It is therefore a model that takes the heterogeneity of the population into account. It is often the case, especially with stated

preference survey, that we have repeated observations for the same individuals. This panel dimension can be considered in the mixed logit¹ model.

More precisely, while working with multinomial logit models, one has to consider three kinds of variables:

- alternative specific variables x_{ij} with generic coefficients β ,
- individual specific variables z_i with alternative specific coefficients γ_j ,
- alternative specific variables w_{ij} with an alternative specific coefficient δ_j .

The satisfaction (utility) index for the alternative j is:

$$V_{ij} = \alpha_j + \beta x_{ij} + \gamma_j z_i + \delta_j w_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad \{1\}$$

Where ε_{ij} is the error term.

Satisfaction being ordinal, only differences are relevant to model the choice of an alternative. This means that the difference between the satisfaction index of two different alternatives j and k is of particular interest:

$$V_{ij} - V_{ik} = (\alpha_j - \alpha_k) + \beta(x_{ij} - x_{ik}) + (\gamma_j - \gamma_k)z_i + (\delta_j w_{ij} - \delta_k w_{ik}) \quad \{2\}$$

The probability of a person i choosing travel option j is given by the following formula {3}:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{\exp^{\lambda V_{ij}}}{\sum_{i=1}^J \exp^{\lambda V_{ij}}} \quad \{3\}$$

Where λ is the scale parameter taken equal to 1.

Based on the above, the variables under consideration as well as the results of the fitted models will be presented in next sections.

10.2 Modelling Software

The statistical analysis and the construction of the multinomial logit models was performed with the use of the programming language R. R is an environment for statistical computing and graphics as well as an integrated suite of software facilities for data manipulation, calculation and graphical display.

R was developed by Ross Ihaka and Ross Gentleman in a project that was conceived in 1992 at the University of Auckland, New Zealand. The first version was released in 1995 and the first stable beta version came up in the year 2000.

The official R software environment is an open-source free software environment within the GNU package, available under the GNU General Public License. It is written primarily in C, Fortran, and R itself (partially self-hosting). Precompiled executables are provided for various operating systems. R has a command line interface. Multiple third-party graphical user interfaces are also available, such as RStudio, an integrated development environment, and Jupyter, a notebook interface. R provides a wide variety of statistical (linear and nonlinear modelling, classical statistical tests, time-series analysis, classification, clustering, etc.) and graphical techniques, and is highly extensible.

¹ Additional information about mixed models can be found in “Stated Choice Methods, Analysis and Applications”, by Louviere J.J., Hensher D.A., Swait J., Cambridge University Press, 2000, and in “Discrete choice methods with Simulation” by Kenneth Train, University of California, Berkeley, 2002

For the construction of the multinomial logit models a specific package of R was used named Mlogit which enables the estimation of the multinomial logit models with individual and/or alternative specific variables. The main extensions of the basic multinomial model (heteroscedastic, nested, and random parameter models) are implemented.

10.3 Model specification

Different multinomial mixed logit models were developed for the different type of users. Users' category was based on the transport mode used during the first mile of the respondents' trip. The four groups that were formed for the development of the multinomial mixed logit models are:

- Bus users
- SOV drivers
- HOV drivers
- Taxi users

SOV and HOV drivers were also examined together since both categories relate to the same transport mode, i.e., car vehicle. SOV and HOV drivers were also further divided based on trip purpose, as it was considered that commuters may have different characteristics from people travelling for different purposes.

At this point, prior to the presentation of the multinomial mixed logit models created, it seems appropriate to present the different variables, both alternative-specific and individual, that was inserted to the model specifications. Note that variables presented are the ones that were found to improve the overall fitness of the model.

Table 10-1: Description of attributes (variables)

Variables	Description	Values
Specific		
Travel option choice		
TIME	Travel Time Home – Station assigned to each alternative (current, CPD/carpool driver, CPR/carpool rider)	Open-ended
COST	Travel Cost Home Station assigned to each alternative (current, CPD/carpool driver, CPR/carpool rider)	Open-ended
PARK	Preferential Parking assigned to each alternative (current, CPD/carpool driver, CPR/carpool rider)	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"
MEETING	Meeting Point assigned to each alternative (current, CPD/carpool driver, CPR/carpool rider)	1 = "Home" 2 = "Out of Home"
FLEX	Flexible time assigned to each alternative (current, CPD/carpool driver, CPR/carpool rider)	1 = "1 hour before" 2 = "3 hours before" 3 = "12 hours before"
Individual		
Trip characteristics (reported)		
TRIP_H_FRE_B	Trip Frequency (for trips with home origin) with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Daily" 2 = "3-4 times a week" 3 = "Once a week" 4 = "2-3 times a month" 5 = "Rarely"
TRIP_PUR_H_B	Trip Purpose (for trips with home origin)	1 = "Commuting"

Variables	Description	Values
	with Metro/Suburban	2 = "Study" 3 = "Personal Reasons" 4 = "Return Home" 5 = "Business" 6 = "Other"
USER	Type of user	1 = "Bus" 2 = "SOV" 3 = "HOV" 4 = "Taxi"
User characteristics		
SEX	Gender	1 = "Woman" 2 = "Man"
AGE_GR	Age Group	1 = "18-25" 2 = "26-35" 3 = "36-45" 4 = "46-55" 5 = "56-65" 6 = "> 65"
OCCUP	Occupation	1 = "Public/Private Sector Employee" 2 = "Freelancer" 3 = "Entrepreneur/ Employer" 4 = "Student" 5 = "Retired" 6 = "Housekeeping" 7 = "Looking for a job" 8 = "Other"
HH_SIZE	Number of Household Members	Open-ended
HH_INC	Average Monthly Household Income	1 = "< 1000€" 2 = "1000€ – 1500€" 3 = "1500€ – 2000€" 4 = ">2000€"
OPINION_CARPPooling	Personal Opinion about Carpooling	1 = "Very Negative" 2 = "Negative" 3 = "Neutral" 4 = "Positive" 5 = "Very Positive"

10.4 Model Results

In this section the results of the different models formulated for each group of users, as previously described, are presented in tabular form. For each model, the parameter estimates (B), the exponential coefficients (exp(B)), the standard error and the z value with the corresponding p-value (showing the significance) of the multinomial mixed logit models are presented along with the McFadden's pseudo-R (ρ) squared which is used for representing the goodness-of-fit of the model. The models show that all the variables (attributes) carry the expected sign; time, cost, preferential parking, meeting point and flexible time (where significant) are all negative, meaning that an increase in one of these variables (attributes) will result to a reduced probability of selecting the specific travel option. The current alternative option is considered as the reference case.

For the individual attributes, and based on the coding as shown in Table 10-1, a negative sign means a reduced probability for the code with the higher value. For example, for attribute SEX (Gender), male is coded as 2 and female as 1. The negative sign on the SEX attribute refers to men who are compared against women.

It must be mentioned that outliers with respect to travel time and/or parking search time were removed from the data set. For example records with travel time values from home to station by private car greater than 30 min and lower than 4 min were considered not realistic for the specific trip and were removed.

Table 10-2: Parameter estimates for all users

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept:CPD	-2.67	0.07	0.29	-9.31	0.00
intercept:CPR	-2.23	0.11	0.31	-7.13	0.00
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.31	0.74	0.02	-15.99	0.00
TIME	-0.03	0.97	0.01	-3.49	0.00
PARK	-0.30	0.74	0.09	-3.33	0.00
MEETING	-0.40	0.67	0.08	-4.91	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week:CPD	-0.57	0.57	0.12	-4.83	0.00
TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week:CPR	0.24	1.27	0.11	2.17	0.03
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.36.45:CPD	-0.34	0.71	0.12	-2.75	0.01
AGE.GR.36.45:CPR	-0.54	0.58	0.13	-4.19	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55:CPD	-0.70	0.50	0.12	-5.92	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55:CPR	-0.83	0.44	0.12	-6.82	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65:CPD	-1.35	0.26	0.19	-7.02	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65:CPR	-1.15	0.32	0.18	-6.22	0.00
AGE.GR.over.65:CPD	-1.00	0.37	0.41	-2.44	0.01

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
AGE.GR.over.65:CPR	-2.31	0.10	0.75	-3.09	0.00
OCCUP.retired:CPD	2.06	7.82	0.82	2.50	0.01
OCCUP.retired:CPR	3.60	36.76	0.75	4.78	0.00
HH.SIZE:CPD	0.20	1.23	0.04	5.81	0.00
HH.SIZE:CPR	0.11	1.12	0.04	3.05	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000:CPD	0.32	1.38	0.10	3.14	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000:CPR	0.31	1.36	0.11	2.88	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral:CPD	1.76	5.78	0.24	7.40	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral:CPR	1.30	3.68	0.27	4.91	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive:CPD	2.47	11.79	0.23	10.63	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive:CPR	2.39	10.88	0.26	9.35	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive:CPD	2.80	16.40	0.24	11.56	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive:CPR	3.04	20.94	0.26	11.60	0.00
Sample	485				
Log-Likelihood	-3255.4				
McFadden R²	0.14				
Likelihood ratio test	chisq = 1056.8 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)				

The model developed for all users, indicates a statistical significant alternative specific constant (ASC), i.e. an a priori preference for one mode when time, cost and other alternative specific variables are equal for all examined options. A negative constant indicates a non-preference of the users for the new alternatives (CPD and CPR) compared to the current mode used. The comparison of the constants among the proposed alternatives, indicate a lesser preference to carpool as a driver compared to carpool as a rider.

Travel time, travel cost, preferential parking and meeting point location appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the travel choice and get a negative sign; this means that an increase in travel time or cost will decrease the probability of choosing this alternative option compared to current transport mode. Based on the value of the exponential coefficients of the alternative specific variables, travel time has the most significant contribution compared to the other attributes.

From variables related to trip characteristics, only trip frequency was found to be statistically significant for all users. More specifically, it was found that people who made the trip under examination 3 to 4 times a week are more likely to choose carpool as a rider and less likely to choose carpool as drivers than the ones who make the trip every day.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, the analysis showed that age, occupation, household size and household income as well as personal opinion about carpooling, were found to have a significant contribution in choosing a travel option amongst the offered ones. People of higher age are less likely to choose carpooling either as drivers or riders compared to younger people whereas people in retirement are more likely to choose carpooling compared to people working as employees. People belonging to higher income classes and people with positive or very

positive opinion about carpooling are also more likely to choose carpooling compared to people of lower income and with a negative opinion about carpooling respectively.

Table 10-3: Parameter estimates for bus users

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept:CPD	0.14	1.15	0.36	0.40	0.04
intercept:CPR	1.26	3.54	0.36	3.53	0.00
Specific choice					
COST	-0.92	0.40	0.18	-5.09	0.00
TIME	-0.11	0.89	0.02	-6.24	0.00
Individual trip					
TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons_CPD	-1.84	0.16	0.60	-3.05	0.00
TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons_CPR	-2.39	0.09	0.53	-4.54	0.00
Individual user					
SEX_CPD	-0.79	0.45	0.22	-3.68	0.00
SEX_CPR	-0.88	0.42	0.18	-5.01	0.00
AGE.GR.36.45_CPD	0.46	1.59	0.22	2.13	0.03
AGE.GR.36.45_CPR	-0.92	0.40	0.22	-4.24	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPD	-0.75	0.47	0.25	-3.05	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPR	-1.20	0.30	0.19	-6.29	0.00
Sample					
	142				
Log-Likelihood					
	-947.9				
McFadden R²					
	0.08				
Likelihood ratio test					
	chisq = 169.88 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)				

The model developed for bus users, indicates a statistical significant alternative specific constant, with a positive sign meaning bus users are more likely to choose carpooling compared to bus and especially carpooling as riders.

Travel time and cost appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the travel option chosen and their parameter values get a negative sign. Bus users are more sensitive to time changes compared to cost changes.

From variables related to trip characteristics, trip purpose was found to be statistically significant for bus users. It was found that people who made the specific trip for personal reasons are less likely to choose carpooling compared to commuters.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, sex and age were found to have a contribution to mode choice. Men are less likely to choose carpooling compared to women bus users. People of higher age are less likely to choose carpooling either as drivers or riders compared to younger people.

Table 10-4: Parameter estimates for SOV drivers

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept:CPD	-1.03	0.36	0.27	-3.78	0.00
intercept:CPR	-1.08	0.34	0.34	-3.19	0.00
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.11	0.90	0.05	-2.20	0.03
TIME	-0.05	0.96	0.02	-2.45	0.01
PARK	-0.28	0.76	0.12	-2.35	0.02
MEETING	-0.55	0.58	0.12	-4.42	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
Individual					
User characteristics					
HH.SIZE:CPD	0.31	1.36	0.06	5.31	0.00
HH.SIZE:CPR	0.24	1.27	0.07	3.55	0.00
HH.VEH:CPD	-0.34	0.71	0.10	-3.29	0.00
HH.VEH:CPR	-0.42	0.66	0.12	-3.56	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative:CPD	-1.24	0.29	0.34	-3.69	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative:CPR	-1.62	0.20	0.61	-2.63	0.01
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive:CPD	1.14	3.14	0.14	7.93	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive:CPR	1.69	5.44	0.19	9.03	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive:CPD	2.31	10.04	0.21	11.12	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive:CPR	2.98	19.62	0.24	12.37	0.00
Sample					
220					
Log-Likelihood					
-1557.5					
McFadden R²					
0.12					
Likelihood ratio test					
chisq = 424.67 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)					

Based on the sign of the alternative specific contrast, SOV users are less likely to choose carpooling either as drivers or riders compared to the use of their private car.

Travel time, cost, preferential parking and meeting point appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the mode choice and have the predicted negative sign. SOV users are more sensitive to travel time and cost compared to the other alternative specific variables.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, household size, number of cars in household and personal opinion about carpooling were found to have a contribution to mode choice. People belonging to households with more members are more likely to choose carpooling while people who have access to a greater number of private vehicles in their household are less likely to choose carpooling. Personal opinion about carpooling also has a positive correlation with choosing carpooling.

Table 10-5: Parameter estimates for HOV drivers

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept: CPD	0.22	1.25	0.43	0.51	0.61
intercept: CPR	-0.55	0.57	0.51	-1.10	0.27
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.24	0.79	0.06	-3.74	0.00
TIME	-0.05	0.95	0.03	-1.72	0.09
PARK	-0.76	0.47	0.19	-3.89	0.00
MEETING	-0.66	0.52	0.19	-3.41	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week_CPD	0.86	2.37	0.39	2.19	0.03
TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week_CPR	1.21	3.36	0.41	2.95	0.00
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.26.35_CPD	1.83	6.24	0.36	5.07	0.00
AGE.GR.26.35_CPR	2.26	9.62	0.38	5.93	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPD	-1.41	0.24	0.28	-4.95	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPR	-0.93	0.39	0.30	-3.12	0.00
OCCUP.freelancer_CPD	-1.67	0.19	0.33	-4.97	0.00
OCCUP.freelancer_CPR	-1.93	0.15	0.39	-4.88	0.00
HH.SIZE_CPD	0.83	2.30	0.13	6.54	0.00
HH.SIZE_CPR	0.89	2.44	0.14	6.42	0.00
HH.VEH_CPD	-1.07	0.34	0.18	-5.90	0.00
HH.VEH_CPR	-0.98	0.37	0.19	-5.15	0.00
Sample					
	79				
Log-Likelihood					
	-593.34				
McFadden R²					
	0.13				
Likelihood ratio test					
	chisq = 183.79 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)				

Based on the sign of the alternative specific contrast, HOV users are less likely to choose carpooling as riders, but they are more likely to choose carpooling as drivers compared to their current transport mode.

Travel time, cost, preferential parking and meeting point appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the mode choice and have the predicted negative sign. HOV users are more sensitive to travel time and cost compared to the other alternative specific variables.

From variables related to trip characteristics, only trip frequency was found to be statistically significant for all users. More specifically, it was found that people who made the trip under examination once per week are more likely to choose carpooling compared to those making the same trip every day.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, age, occupation, household size and number of cars in household were found to have a contribution to mode choice. People of higher age and people working as freelancers are less likely to choose carpooling compared to younger people and people with other occupations respectively. People belonging to households with more members are more likely to choose carpooling while people who have access to a greater number of private vehicles in their household are less likely to choose carpooling

Table 10-6: Parameter estimates for Taxi users

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept:CPD	1.54	4.67	0.68	2.25	0.02
intercept:CPR	2.95	19.19	0.65	4.53	0.00
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.76	0.47	0.11	-7.00	0.00
TIME	-0.14	0.87	0.08	-1.77	0.05
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons:CPD	-2.23	0.11	0.61	-3.68	0.00
TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons:CPR	-1.68	0.19	0.43	-3.92	0.00
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.46.55:CPD	2.16	8.69	0.52	4.13	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55:CPR	1.47	4.35	0.41	3.55	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000:CPD	-3.88	0.02	0.84	-4.61	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000:CPR	-4.14	0.02	0.75	-5.52	0.00
HH.INC.over.2000:CPD	-4.83	0.01	0.74	-6.53	0.00
HH.INC.over.2000:CPR	-4.35	0.01	0.66	-6.56	0.00
KNOW.CARPOOLING2:CPD	1.44	4.20	0.47	3.06	0.00
KNOW.CARPOOLING2:CPR	1.40	4.06	0.38	3.66	0.00
Sample					
44					
Log-Likelihood					
-257.23					
McFadden R²					
0.23					
Likelihood ratio test					
chisq = 150.88 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)					

The model developed for taxi users indicates a very strong a preference for carpooling all other being equal especially as riders compared to their current transport mode. Travel time and cost appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the mode choice and get a negative sign. Based on the value of the exponential coefficients of the alternative specific variables, travel time have the most significant contribution.

From variables related to trip characteristics, only trip purpose was found to be statistically significant. More specifically, it was found that people travelling for personal reasons are less likely to choose carpooling, especially as riders, compared to commuters.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, age, household income and familiarity with carpooling were found to have a contribution to mode choice. For this user category, people between 46-55 years old are more likely to choose carpooling compared to younger people, especially carpooling as drivers. People of higher income are less likely to choose carpooling either as drivers or riders compared to people of lower income while people who are familiar with the concept of carpooling are more likely to choose such a system.

Table 10-7: Parameter estimates SOV & HOV drivers

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept_CPD	-2.25	0.10	0.32	-7.03	0.00
intercept_CPR	-2.49	0.08	0.42	-5.97	0.00
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.12	0.89	0.04	-3.08	0.00
TIME	-0.06	0.95	0.02	-3.69	0.00
PARK	-0.33	0.72	0.10	-3.18	0.00
MEETING	-0.49	0.61	0.11	-4.65	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.36.45_CPD	-0.32	0.73	0.15	-2.18	0.03
AGE.GR.36.45_CPR	-0.38	0.69	0.17	-2.27	0.02
AGE.GR.46.55_CPD	-0.48	0.62	0.14	-3.43	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPR	-0.46	0.63	0.16	-2.89	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPD	-1.18	0.31	0.22	-5.44	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPR	-0.44	0.64	0.21	-2.07	0.04
HH.SIZE_CPD	0.25	1.29	0.04	5.66	0.00
HH.SIZE_CPR	0.20	1.22	0.05	3.96	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral_CPD	1.41	4.10	0.25	5.70	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral_CPR	1.31	3.70	0.34	3.81	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive_CPD	2.41	11.12	0.24	9.89	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive_CPR	2.77	16.03	0.33	8.39	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very_positive_CPD	3.07	21.61	0.27	11.49	0.00
OPINION.CARPOOLING.very_positive_CPR	3.48	32.46	0.35	9.94	0.00
Sample					
299					
Log-Likelihood					
-2098.4					
McFadden R²					
0.11					
Likelihood ratio test					
chisq = 511.59 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)					

The model constructed for both SOV and HOV users indicates an a priori preference to the current transport mode, in the specific case car vehicle, compared to carpooling.

Travel time, cost, preferential parking and meeting point appear to have a statistically significant contribution to the mode choice and have a negative sign. Travel time and cost have the most significant contribution to transport mode choice.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, age, household size and personal opinion about carpooling were found to have a contribution to mode choice. Older people are less likely to choose carpooling compared to older ones especially carpooling as drivers. People of higher age are less likely to choose carpooling either as drivers or riders compared to younger people while people belonging to a household with more members are more likely to choose the specific alternative. As expected, people with a positive or very positive opinion about carpooling are more likely to choose it, especially as riders.

Table 10-8: Parameter estimates SOV & HOV commuting

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept_CPD	0.42	1.52	0.21	1.99	0.05
intercept_CPR	0.66	1.93	0.25	2.66	0.01
Specific					
Travel option choice					
TIME	-0.05	0.95	0.01	-3.67	0.00
PARK	-0.32	0.73	0.11	-2.97	0.00
MEETING	-0.61	0.55	0.11	-5.65	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.36.45_CPD	-0.54	0.58	0.15	-3.68	0.00
AGE.GR.36.45_CPR	-0.46	0.63	0.16	-2.82	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPD	-0.74	0.48	0.15	-5.06	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPR	-0.68	0.51	0.16	-4.16	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPD	-1.27	0.28	0.21	-5.95	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPR	-0.80	0.45	0.22	-3.62	0.00
AGE.GR.over.65_CPD	-1.33	0.27	0.42	-3.18	0.00
AGE.GR.over.65_CPR	-2.46	0.09	0.75	-3.26	0.00
HH.SIZE_CPD	0.15	1.16	0.04	3.40	0.00
HH.SIZE_CPR	0.11	1.12	0.05	2.28	0.02
Sample					
246					
Log-Likelihood					
-2059.4					
McFadden R²					
0.03					
Likelihood ratio test					
chisq = 121.82 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)					

Table 10-9: Parameter estimates for SOV & HOV study, personal, other purposes

Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
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Variables	B	Exp(B)	Std. Error	z-value	Sig.
intercept_CPD	-0.67	0.51	0.37	-1.82	0.05
intercept_CPR	-1.63	0.20	0.41	-3.99	0.00
Specific					
Travel option choice					
COST	-0.71	0.49	0.11	-6.19	0.00
Individual					
Trip characteristics					
TRIP_H_FRE_3_4_times_week_CPD	-2.07	0.13	0.37	-5.65	0.00
TRIP_H_FRE_3_4_times_week_CPR	-1.94	0.14	0.40	-4.85	0.00
Individual					
User characteristics					
AGE.GR.46.55_CPD	-2.50	0.08	0.45	-5.61	0.00
AGE.GR.46.55_CPR	-2.79	0.06	0.50	-5.58	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPD	-2.99	0.05	0.56	-5.34	0.00
AGE.GR.56.65_CPR	-1.94	0.14	0.56	-3.48	0.00
OCCUP.freelancer_CPD	-1.25	0.29	0.51	-2.45	0.01
OCCUP.freelancer_CPR	-2.46	0.09	0.66	-3.75	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000_CPD	3.60	36.48	0.59	6.06	0.00
HH.INC.1500.2000_CPR	3.83	46.10	0.63	6.13	0.00
HH.INC.over.2000_CPD	1.98	7.23	0.38	5.20	0.00
HH.INC.over.2000_CPR	2.62	13.72	0.42	6.27	0.00
Sample					
54					
Log-Likelihood					
-369.95					
McFadden R²					
0.20					
Likelihood ratio test					
chisq = 181.05 (p.value = < 2.22e-16)					

Concerning the models formulated for SOV and HOV users based on trip purpose, it can be concluded that commuters indicate an a-priori preference for carpooling in contrast to SOV and HOV users traveling for other purposes.

From variables related to trip characteristics, only trip frequency was found to be statistically significant for trip purposes related to study, personal and other purposes. More specifically, it was found that people who made the trip under examination 3 to 4 times a week are less likely to choose carpooling compared to people who make the specific trip every day.

Based on the alternative specific variables, commuters are influenced by travel time, preferential parking and meeting point while transport mode choice of users traveling for other purposes is influenced only by travel cost.

Regarding the investigation of the user specific attributes, age and household size were found to have a contribution to mode choice for commuters. Older people are less likely to choose carpooling compared to younger people and people belonging to a household with more members are more

likely to choose the specific alternative. For other trip purposes, age, occupation and household income were found to be statistically significant. Again, older people are less likely to choose carpooling and people working as freelancers, compared to other occupations, are also less likely to choose carpooling. People with higher incomes are more likely to choose carpooling, especially as riders.

10.5 Willingness to Pay and Willingness to Accept

The coefficients of the attribute variables in the models are not directly interpretable, but dividing them by the price parameter (coefficient), we get monetary values of the Willingness-To-Pay (WTP) or the Willingness to Accept (WTA), in order to gain or lose one unit of the respective travel option attribute. The term WTP applies when the user must pay an amount in order to get certain benefits such as time gains, more comfort, better reliability, etc. The term WTA is used when the user will have to give up something such as accepting time loss, or comfort in order to enjoy another benefit.

Given that the alternative specific constants in the choice models have negative signs for the SOV and HOV categories, choosing either the CPD or the CPR travel option, which is associated with reduced travel cost compared to their current option, means that they have to accept that they will give up something. SOV drivers give up the comfort of travelling alone from home to the station, whereas HOV drivers need to travel with a third to them person. In addition they may have to make a small detour in order to pick up their new rider resulting to a slightly longer trip duration. Finally, they may need to make arrangements with their rider for the return trip home, which is an additional issue to deal with.

For taxi drivers the alternative specific constants in the respective choice models have a positive sign, meaning that they have a preference all other being equal to choose the CPD or the CPR option. In these cases, the trip maker will give up the comfort of travelling alone and perhaps the departure time of his choice in order to reduce the travel cost their currently pay. This is again a WTA situation, since the users trade a qualitative attribute against a price cut.

The only WTP case applies for bus users who are willing to pay a higher price for the trip from home to the station in order to gain time and comfort since their will replace the longer bus travel by private car travel.

The Value of Time (VoT) for every category of trip makes is calculated by finding the ratio of the parameters of travel time over time cost. The specific result is expressed in Euros per min and by multiplying by 60 we get the VoT in euros per hour.

Table 10-10 shows the average Value of Time for different categories of trip makers for their trip segment from home to metro/suburban rail station.

Table 10-10: Value of Time for all models (€/hour)

		Category	Bus	SOV	HOV	Taxi
VoT	7.43	25.62	12.10	11.10		

VoT denotes the amount in euros that a user would be willing to pay in order to save time one minute or one hour, or the amount they would accept as compensation for time lost in case of a symmetric response.

The Value of Time for SOV users (25.62) is the highest one of all categories, whereas the VoT for bus (7.43) users is the lowest one as expected. These figures correspond to 0.427 €/min and 0.124 €/min

respectively. This means that SOV users are willing in average to pay or to accept 42.7 euro cents for each min they gain or lose respectively. The respective figures for HOV drivers and taxi drivers are in between.

In general the resulted VoT figures are considered rational and close to the values obtained from other studies or surveys in the Greater Athens area with the exception of SOV drivers. For this particular category the resulting VoT appears to be high enough. In a SP survey conducted for ATTIKO METRO in 2006, the VoT per person for light vehicles was found to be 7 € on average. According to another survey made along Attiki Odos the VoT for passengers of light vehicles was found to vary from 7.0 to 12.0 €/h.

However, it should be mentioned that the SOV sample surveyed does not represent a typical population group in the Athens area. Residents in the areas along the metro/suburban rail corridor belong to higher than average income classes, which translates to higher VoT. SoV and HoV users afford the luxury of leaving their car parked for 6-10 hours at the metro station and riding urban rail to their final destination. Apparently, they could be considered as a special group of commuters in the greater Athens area.

For the other categories the VoT figures resulted are very close to the ones available from other sources.

Regarding the WTP for other attributes, Table 10-11 presents the WTP values for preferential parking and for Meeting point of Carpooling driver and rider. The latter, depending on where the two trip makers are met, i.e. at a point convenient to both or at a point requiring some additional walking time for the rider and/or a short detour for the driver results to longer travel times for both carpoolers by 2-4 min. Furthermore, it creates some inconvenience to both of them.

Table 10-11: Willingness to Pay (WTP) for Preferential Parking and Meeting Location (€/hour)

Category		Bus	SOV	HOV	Taxi
Preferential Parking	N/A	2.6	2.7	N/A	
Meeting Location	N/A	5.0	3.2	N/A	

Travel cost and travel time elasticities

Based on model results, the elasticities for travel time and travel cost can be calculated. Elasticity is defined as the percentage change in one variable that is related to the change in another variable by one percentage point. The elasticity values estimated by the mixed multinomial logistic regression models make it possible to assess the degree of sensitivity of demand to changes in the various factors affecting it, in this case time and travel costs, and thus to evaluate the various policies that can be applied in the transport sector.

Travel cost is expressed in euros whereas travel time in minute. By increasing either one of them or both of them we can calculate the new probability of a trip maker falling in one of the four categories, to select one of the three available travel options.

The general formula for the calculation of the (direct point) elasticities E of each individual q in a basic discrete choice scheme can be written, according to Louviere et al and Dunne, as² :

² Louviere J.J., Hensher D.A., Swait J., “Stated Choice Methods”, Cambridge University Press, 2000,

$$E_{X_{ikq}}^{P_{iq}} = \frac{\partial P_{iq}}{\partial P_{ikq}} \cdot \frac{X_{ikq}}{P_{iq}} \quad \{1\}$$

Where: q is the individual who chooses alternative i.

Using the quotient rule of the derivatives (i.e., $\partial e^{az} / \partial Z = ae^{az}$), equation {1} can be written as:

$$E_{X_{ikq}}^{P_{iq}} = \beta_{ik} X_{ikq} (1 - P_{iq}) \quad \{2\}$$

From equation {2} it can be easily concluded that direct elasticity approaches zero as P_{jq} approaches unity and approaches $\beta_{ik} X_{ikq}$ as P_{jq} approaches to zero. In order to obtain aggregate elasticities, an approach known as “sample enumeration method” was used since the usage of sample average values for the X_{ikq} or the \hat{P}_{iq} (average estimated P_j) is not correct for the non-linear logit models. In the sample enumeration approach, individual probability is first calculated and then aggregate by weighting each individual elasticity by the individuals’ estimated probability of choice (Louviere et al, 2000).

The mathematical expression of the above is written as:

$$E_{X_{jkq}}^{\bar{P}_i} = \left(\sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{P}_{iq} E_{X_{jkq}}^{P_{iq}} \right) / \sum_{q=1}^Q \hat{P}_{iq} \quad \{3\}$$

Where: \hat{P}_{iq} is an estimated choice probability and

\bar{P}_i refers to the aggregate probability of choice probability i .

Table 10-12 presents the travel cost and the travel time elasticities, for all models developed, provided of course these calculations are feasible.

Table 10-12: Travel time and cost elasticities

	Current mode	CPD	CPR
Travel Time Elasticities			
Bus	-0.92	-1.36	-1.17
SOV	-0.42	-0.46	-0.59
HOV	-0.51	-0.45	-0.57
Taxi	-1.14	-1.93	-0.86
All	-0.23	-0.28	-0.29
Travel Cost Elasticities			
Bus	0.00	-10.99	-1.63
SOV	-0.24	-1.01	-0.16
HOV	-0.64	-2.22	-0.36
Taxi	-1.92	-10.46	-0.83
All	-0.41	-3.14	-0.45

From this Table, it can be concluded that:

Dunne J. P. (1984), Elasticity measures and disaggregate choice models, Journal of Transport Economics and Poli-cy, p.p. 189-197

- Bus and taxi users are more affected by an increase in travel time and travel cost for the option of carpooling as a driver.
- SOV and HOV users are less affected by a similar increase in travel time and travel cost for the option of carpooling as a driver.
- For all users' categories, travel cost is more significant than travel time for carpooling as a driver while the opposite applies for carpooling as riders with the exception of bus users.

11. Overview and Interpretation of Main Findings

11.1 Overview of Main Findings

The following tables 11-1 and 11-2 present an overview of the models developed for the purposes of the survey i.e. for determining the probability of choosing either the option of becoming a carpool driver (CPD) or a carpool rider (CPR) against the current travel option, for the first/last mile segment of a trip in which the main segment is made by metro or suburban rail. The models are based on data and information of trip makers who live at areas close to the urban rail corridor of the Eastern Attica Region and use for the specific first/last mile segment one of the following travel modes:

- CAT1: Bus
- CAT2: SOV (Single Occupancy vehicle)
- CAT3: HOV (High Occupancy vehicle)
- CAT4: Taxi

Table 11-1 presents the models for the CPD travel option and Table 11-2 the models for the CPR option. It is reminded that attribute values for time and cost in these models refer not to absolute values but to differences from the respective values of the current travel option which is the reference option for the MNL choice modelling exercises.

Table 11-1: Overview of MNL choice models for choosing CPD travel option for the first/last mile

Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
Bus	$V_{CPD} = 0.14 - 0.92 * COST_{CPD} - 0.11 * TIME_{CPD} - 1.84 * TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons - 0.79 * SEX + 0.46 * AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.75 * AGE.GR.46.55$
SOV	$V_{CPD} = -1.03 - 0.11 * COST_{CPD} - 0.05 * TIME_{CPD} - 0.28 * PARK_{CPD} - 0.55 * MEETING_{CPD} + 0.31 * HH.SIZE - 0.34 * HH.VEH - 1.24 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative + 1.14 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.31 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$
HOV	$V_{CPD} = 0.22 - 0.24 * COST_{CPD} - 0.05 * TIME_{CPD} - 0.76 * PARK_{CPD} - 0.66 * MEETING_{CPD} + 0.86 * TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week + 1.83 * AGE.GR.26.35 - 1.41 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.67 * OCCUP.freelancer + 0.83 * HH.SIZE - 1.07 * HH.VEH$
Taxi	$V_{CPD} = 1.54 - 0.76 * COST_{CPD} - 0.14 * TIME_{CPD} - 2.23 * TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons + 2.16 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 3.88 * HH.INC.1500.2000 - 4.83 * HH.INC.over.2000 + 1.44 * KNOW.CARPOOLING$
All	$V_{CPD} = -2.67 - 0.31 * COST_{CPD} - 0.03 * TIME_{CPD} - 0.30 * PARK_{CPD} - 0.40 * MEETING_{CPD} - 0.57 * TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week - 0.34 * AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.70 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.35 * AGE.GR.56.65 - 1.00 * AGE.GR.over.65 + 2.06 * OCCUP.retired + 0.20 * HH.SIZE + 0.32 * HH.INC.1500.2000 + 1.76 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral + 2.47 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.80 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$

Table 11-2: Overview of MNL choice models for choosing CPR travel option for the first/last mile

Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
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Trip makers category	Model expression for Travel Option CPD
Bus	$V_{CPR} = 1.26 - 0.92 * COST_{CPR} - 0.11 * TIME_{CPR} - 2.39 * TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons - 0.88 * SEX - 0.92 * AGE.GR.36.45 - 1.20 * AGE.GR.46.55$
SOV	$V_{CPR} = -1.08 - 0.11 * COST_{CPR} - 0.05 * TIME_{CPR} - 0.28 * PARK_{CPR} - 0.55 * MEETING_{CPR} + 0.24 * HH.SIZE - 0.42 * HH.VEH - 1.62 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.negative + 1.69 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 2.98 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$
HOV	$V_{CPR} = -0.55 - 0.24 * COST_{CPR} - 0.05 * TIME_{CPR} - 0.76 * PARK_{CPR} - 0.66 * MEETING_{CPR} + 1.21 * TRIP.H.FRE.1.time.week + 2.26 * AGE.GR.26.35 - 0.93 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.93 * OCCUP.freelancer + 0.89 * HH.SIZE - 0.98 * HH.VEH$
Taxi	$V_{CPR} = 2.95 - 0.76 * COST_{CPR} - 0.14 * TIME_{CPR} - 1.68 * TRIP.PUR.H.B.personal.reasons + 1.47 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 4.14 * HH.INC.1500.2000 - 4.35 * HH.INC.over.2000 + 1.40 * KNOW.CARPOOLING$
All	$V_{CPR} = -2.67 - 0.31 * COST_{CPR} - 0.03 * TIME_{CPR} - 0.30 * PARK_{CPR} - 0.40 * MEETING_{CPR} + 0.24 * TRIP.H.FRE.B.3.4.times.week - 0.54 * AGE.GR.36.45 - 0.83 * AGE.GR.46.55 - 1.15 * AGE.GR.56.65 - 2.31 * AGE.GR.over.65 + 3.60 * OCCUP.retired + 0.11 * HH.SIZE + 0.31 * HH.INC.1500.2000 + 1.30 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.neutral + 2.39 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.positive + 3.04 * OPINION.CARPOOLING.very.positive$

The above models can be used for finding both the Willingness to Pay or the Willingness to Accept Carpooling either as a driver or as a rider in the area of Attica Region depending on which is the current travel option for the trip from home to the station or vice versa. To do this the models must be fed with the right attribute values which will return an output value (Utility or satisfaction) that exceeds the value of the alternative specific constant.

As an indicative example, an SOV user whose travel time including parking search time is equal to 15 min and the travel cost is 4 euros including parking cost, will change his/her current transport mode and will choose travelling as a CPD only if the travel cost is reduced by 1.5 € or more and at the same time he/she is granted preferential parking and at the same time the meeting place is convenient for him. The same trip maker will choose to travel as a CPR if the travel cost is reduced to half and at the same time enjoys preferential parking and convenient meeting location.

The model results favour trip makers with high travel cost and long travel time and parking search time.

Figure 11-1 depicts on a cost – time diagram the respondents’ travel choices’ based on the cost and time combination. The depiction uses colours to distinguish choices of the respondents according to the current mode used to travel from home to station.

Figure 11-1: Illustration of Respondents' choices on a cost-time two-dimension diagram

It can be seen in this illustration that bus users, who continue to choose bus for their trip from home to station, even when carpool travel options are available, have zero travel cost because they do not have to pay any fare for this trip-segment by bus.

Figure 11-2 shows a similar diagram with the choices of the respondents belonging only to CAT1, i.e. the ones who currently use bus.

Figure 11-2: Illustration of CAT 1 Respondents' choices on a cost-time two dimension diagram

Figures 11-3 to 11-5 depict similar illustrations showing respondents' choices belonging to CAT2, CAT3 and CAT4 respectively.

Figure 11-3: Illustration of CAT2 Respondents' choices on a cost-time two dimension diagram

Figure 11-4: Illustration of CAT3 Respondents' choices on a cost-time two dimension diagram

Figure 11-5: Illustration of CAT4 Respondents' choices on a cost-time two dimension diagram

11.2 Interpretation of Findings

The models developed regarding the choice of the persons belonging to the specific categories surveyed for shifting or not from their current travel mode to a new carpooling mode either as drivers or riders, provide interesting and useful findings which can be exploited by the respective policy makers and the agencies providing Public Transport services. The findings are primarily exploitable in the case of the eastern region of Attica where the survey took place. However, they can also be of interest in other areas, given that the general travel and other socioeconomic conditions are similar.

The research and model development findings indicate that carpooling either as a driver (CPD) or as a rider (CPR) is not the preferred travel option for trip makers driving alone from home to the metro/suburban rail station where they park their vehicle and board on the urban rail system. The models for this specific category show that all other being equal, the utility they receive (the point where the utility curve intersects with the horizontal axis, i.e. the constant term of the utility function) is negative for both options. Therefore, the expected cost and/or time benefits along with additional benefits such as the preferential parking for carpoolers should overcome the respective values. Solo drivers when considering becoming car poolers either as drivers or riders mainly trade the expected travel cost reductions with loss of comfort and/or convenience since they will have to make a detour and most likely accept a small delay in order to travel with another car pooler.

For drivers with a passenger, the situation is slightly different. In the CPD case the constant is positive, whereas for the CPR case it is negative. This means that for those who drive to the station with passenger(s) the travel option as a CPR is preferable compared to their current option. This could be attributed to the fact that they do not have to use their car every day, and perhaps somebody else from their household may take benefit of this.

For the taxi users, both CPD and CPR options are preferred against their current one, all other being equal. The main reason for this finding seems to be the non-dependency of the taxi search which seems to be a burden during rush hours at those geographical areas.

Finally for current bus users from home to the station, both alternative specific constants are positive, meaning that the bus is inferior to both carpooling travel options. In fact, the carpooling options are based on a trade-off between travel time (by bus) and cost (being a CPD or CPR) as well as time and convenience (car instead of bus).

Another interesting finding by looking at the user characteristics is that the car ownership index (COI) of bus users is just 1.15 when the average number of drivers licence holders is 1.86. Substituting bus by the CPR option looks a logical choice since they do not have to use their car as CPD.

Table 11-3 presents the COI values, the number of HH licence holders and the average HH size per category of users who participated in the second phase of the survey.

Table 11-3: Overview of specific HH characteristics per users' category

Category of users	Bus	SOV	HOV	Taxi
Car Ownership Index	1.15	1.82	1.76	1.34
Number of Driver License holders in the HH	1.86	2.19	2.16	1.91
Household Size	3.18	3.18	3.04	3.20

Regarding the rather high values of time for the SOV category, which are derived from the developed models, the explanation lies with the fact that the majority of the specific trip makers

belong to high income classes. Furthermore, the fact that the specific first or last mile trip segment is relatively short in time terms, leads to higher time values. Should the models had developed for the entire trip from initial origin to final destination, the values of time would be definitely lower.

Based on the elasticities derived from the models, it turns out that travel time is elastic for current bus users for both new travel options of CPD and CPR, meaning that a change by one minute in the travel time will have a stronger effect in the possibility of becoming either CPD or CPR. Elasticity is stronger for choosing CPD as compared to choosing CPR. Travel time is inelastic for SOV and HOV categories whereas is elastic for taxi users

When it comes to travel cost, this attribute is strongly elastic for bus users as expected. The same applies to taxi users, whereas for SOV and HOV travel cost is elastic for the CPD option and inelastic for the CPR option.

The fact that from the analysis made, it turns out that there are no significant differences among male and female trip makers towards the carpooling preferences, except for the bus users' category, means that there is no need for differentiating potential policies or incentives amongst them for the private car users. Regarding bus users, women seem to be more favourable in becoming carpoolers than men.

Finally, trip makers coming from households with low number of available vehicles, seem that they are in favour of becoming carpool riders than those who come from HH with more available cars. It seems that the difference between the Car Ownership Index and number of persons holding a driver's license may have an effect on the trip makers preferences. The above finding can be explained as an effort to maximise utility at the household level - since the car that remains at home can be utilised by another family member - rather than at the individual level. However, efforts to introduce new attributes addressing the ratio among Car Ownership Index and number of driving licenses did not return any confirming results.

12. Conclusions and Recommendations

12.1 Conclusions

The analysis of the results derived from the MNL logit models determining the probability a trip maker from home to a metro/suburban station to change their current travel mode and choose instead a car pool option either as driver (CPD) or as a rider (CPR), in conjunction with the interpretation of the research findings presented in the previous sectors, lead to several conclusions. It is reminded that the trip makers surveyed belong to four discrete categories namely bus users (BUS), solo drivers (SOV) who park their car at the station area, drivers with passengers (HOV) who also park their car at the station area, and taxi users. It is also reminded that the surveyed trip comprises the first or the last segment - assuming an analogy between first mile of a home outward trip and last mile of a return home inward trip - of a journey consisting of at least three segments, the second one being the trip with the metro or the suburban rail. Finally, it is clarified that trip purposes are limited to commuting, travelling for study and for personal reasons only. Business trips have not been surveyed. Similarly, trip makers using company cars or their own car with their expenses covered, were not included in the survey. The survey took place at two stations, namely Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi.

The most important of the conclusions drawn are as follows.

1. Solo drivers (SOV) comprise the vast majority of the metro/suburban rail systems users who board at the stations of Doukissis Plakentias and Koropi. These trip makers park their car at a parking spot either at the stations parking lots or at the surrounding area. The average total travel time to reach the station from home is approximately 17 min and the average travel cost is 4.5 € without parking cost. Average parking search time is 4 min. The vast majority of SOV users do not pay for parking.
2. The second largest percentage pertains to persons arriving at the stations by bus. The average total travel time to reach the station from home is approximately 24 min. The travel cost is practically zero, since bus users pay the integrated fare which applies for riding to both metro and suburban rail.
3. HOV users and taxi users comprise very small portions of the total passengers arriving at the two stations This is reflected to the smaller samples surveyed. HOV users also park their car at the stations. The average travel time and cost is respectively 19.5 min and 4.5 €. Regarding taxi users the respective figures are 15.5 min and 5.8 €
4. For bus users the most important factors which were found to be negative are in descending order a) Low bus frequency, b) lack of information, c) high bus occupancy, d) long bus journey time, long walking distance to bus stop, e) exposure to weather conditions, f) Lack of shelters.
5. The majority of trip makers arriving at the stations are holders of the OASA Public Transport card (66%).
6. Trip makers arriving at the stations by bus are willing to shift to carpooling either as drivers or as riders. Given that they are not charged an extra fare for their trip to the station, but they make use of the integrated fare, the incentive to become carpool users lies with a time saving in their home-station trip. For an average time saving of 9 min or 38%, 89% of respondents stated that they would prefer to become carpool drivers (22%) or carpool riders (67%). Should the time saving raises to 66.6% an additional 5% will be directed to the CPD and CPR options.
7. Solo drivers (SOV) appear to be willing to become carpoolers as well but at a lesser degree. For a 50% reduction in travel cost (split equally between the carpoolers) and a similar travel

time figure as in the current travel option, the respondents are divided almost in equal shares among the three travel options. More specifically 32% of the solo drivers will continue driving alone to the station, 34% will become carpool drivers (CPD) and the remaining 32% will become carpool riders (CPR). For additional cuts in the travel cost for the car poolers there is only a marginal increase in the above percentage figures by 2% - 3%. This is fully justified by the low elasticity value calculated for the particular category of trip makers.

8. For HOV users the situation is different, given that these drivers in a way act already as carpoolers, although they may not ride together with a third person but with a relative or friend. This group of trip makers state that they will become carpool drivers (64%) if the travel cost halves the travel time remaining unchanged or carpool riders (30%) for the same conditions. Only 6% will continue behaving as currently. Both travel cost and travel time are inelastic for the CPR option. However, the travel cost elasticity for CPD is highly elastic and this explains the large percentage of HOV users choosing the CPD option.
9. Finally for taxi users both travel cost and time are elastic for the CPD and CPR travel options. The elasticity is stronger for the CPD option.
10. The Value of Time for SOV users was determined to approximately 25 €/h, which is considered high enough when compared with values from other studies or surveys. However, there are two good reasons for this discrepancy; firstly, the sample of people surveyed belong to a rather high class in terms of income and secondly, the trip length and time are both short, thus resulting to higher VoT. The latter finding is consistent with international bibliography on this matter.
11. The VoT for HOV was determined to approximately 12 €/h, for taxi users to 11 €/h, and for bus users to 7.5 €/h, figures which are considered as realistic. The latter may be slightly higher, but again it refers to a short trip.
12. The Willingness to Pay (WTP) in order to secure preferential parking was calculated to 2.6 €. This is rather a low value but it is justified by the fact that the vast majority of the trip makers who park at or near the station, do not pay any parking charges. The lack of any parking control and enforcement in the surrounding areas favours free and illegal parking.
13. No significant differences exist between male and female trip makers towards carpooling travel options with the exception of bus users.
14. Overall it seems that the majority of the persons interviewed based on the models developed are in favour of a carpooling travel option as a rider and then as a carpool driver.
15. Carpooling options favour car users riding Metro/Suburban rail or shifting to these modes, thus increasing ridership of urban rail, whereas discourage bus users continue using this mode to access Metro/Suburban rail stations.

By applying the choice models developed, it is possible to estimate the number of users who will change their current travel option with one of the two proposed travel options, i.e. becoming carpool drivers or carpool riders for their trip segment home to metro/suburban rail station. The use of each model developed must be applied to the population belonging to each discrete category of trip makers according to their current transport choice, i.e. PT bus user, SOV, HOV or taxi user. Knowledge of other characteristics of the population leaving in the areas around the metro/suburban rail tracks such as gender, age group etc. which were found to be significant for the preferred travel option choice, will provide a better estimation of the future demand for carpooling and thus they may facilitate policy making decisions by ATTIKO METRO SA or by others involved agencies and stakeholders.

12.2 Recommendations

Carpool travel options (driver or rider) mainly aim at increasing vehicle occupancy and thus reducing circulation of cars and consequently traffic. The main target is private car users who commute frequently and suffer high travel costs and possibly long travel times due to congestion. Several additional measures are introduced along with carpooling to facilitate and provide incentives to potential car poolers, such as preferential parking, guaranteed ride home, carpooling matching platforms, etc. Given the complexity of this issue, carpooling policies should be targeted and realistic and need to be based on exhaustive research and investigation. The RAIL2RIDE project as a part of the SHIFT2RAIL initiative at the EU level, attempts to find ways for increasing rail usage and attract trip makers from other less sustainable modes to rail modes. With respect to sub-urban areas, focus is given to areas not well covered by other PT modes such as buses, mainly due to the high bus service cost, low frequency and/or not satisfactory service availability in terms of service hours per day.

In this respect Ridesharing/carpooling is considered an appealing option for meeting the SHIFT2RAIL goals, especially in cases such the eastern area of Attica Region in Greece. The RP/SP survey carried out in this geographical area indicates that there is a critical mass of trip makers – mainly commuters - who use on a regular basis metro or suburban rail and make the first or the last trip segment by others transport modes and who will be willing to shift to carpooling for this segment either as drivers or riders. Supplementary measures such as preferential parking and carpooling matching platforms have an additive effect. In addition, it is anticipated that induced carpooling demand may result once the right policies are designed and implemented. A successful carpooling policy requires of course among other the examination of technical, legal, social and cultural aspects.

Having all these in mind, the following recommendations can be suggested.

1. The involved authorities/agencies which have the responsibility to implement carpooling schemes in the Attica Region should consider all relevant aspects affecting ridesharing success. Based on the surveys and the choice model results, it turns out that given the right incentives in terms of travel cost, parking cost and availability and tools for finding the most suitable carpool matches, a significant percentage of trip makers who currently use either bus, or car or taxi could become potential carpool drivers or riders.
2. ATTIKO METRO SA, in case they decide to forward carpool plans along with other involved authorities, will have to secure adequate parking spaces close to the metro stations. Furthermore, they will have to assign a study about the parking fees in all stations in conjunction with the incentives they plan to provide.
3. A full-scale study is required in order to determine the volume of potential carpoolers from each geographical area of the Attica Region per category (CAT1, CAT2, CAT3 and CAT4). The study should include an extended RP and SP survey, and should be executed in stages in order to simplify the whole process. Estimation of carpoolers must be based on the new census demographic data and also on recent PT data and ATTIKO METRO models.
4. In addition to the above, mixed car-sharing/carpooling schemes should be studied. Such schemes help overcome certain disadvantages associated with carpooling, since guaranteed ride home stops becoming a major issue.
5. The involved authorities and stakeholders need to examine in depth all technical, legal and technological aspects that turn into real problems if not considered well in advance.

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APPENDIX A: Screen Shots of RP and SP Questionnaire

First Phase

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 1

* Κωδικός συνέντευξης:

* Ημερομηνία | Ώρα:

* Σταθμός συνέντευξης:

Δουκίσσης Πλακεντίας

Κορωπί

* Τοποθεσία συνέντευξης:

Πλατφόρμα σταθμού

Εντός σταθμού

Χώρος Parking

Πέριξ σταθμού σε δρόμο

Εντός συρμού

Εντός λεωφορείου

Figure A-1: RP Questionnaire – Page 1

*Είστε κάτοχος διπλώματος οδήγησης;

Ναι Όχι

*Διαθέτετε επιβατικό όχημα;

Ναι Όχι

*Διαθέτετε κάρτα ΟΑΣΑ απεριορίστων διαδρομών;

Ναι Όχι

*Ποιός είναι ο σκοπός της μετακίνησής σας;

- Εργασία
- Σπουδές
- Προσωπικοί λόγοι (ψώνια, ψυχαγωγία, άθληση, κοινωνικοί λόγοι κ.α.)
- Επιστροφή σπίτι
- Στα πλαίσια της εργασίας
- Άλλο:

Προηγούμενη

Υποβολή

Figure A-2: RP Questionnaire – Page 2

*Πρόκειται να επιβιβαστείτε στο Μετρό ή Προαστιακό στον σταθμό αυτόν;

Ναι Όχι

*Με ποιο μέσο φτάσατε;

Λεωφορείο ΟΑΣΑ

Μόνος μου με το όχημα μου που πάρκαρα στην περιοχή του σταθμού

Με το όχημα μου που πάρκαρα στην περιοχή του σταθμού και με συνεπιβάτη/τες

Ταξί

Μετρό

Προαστιακό

Με τα πόδια

Με όχημα άλλου

Άλλο:

Figure A-3: RP Questionnaire – Page 3

*Απο πού ξεκινήσατε αρχικά μέχρι να φτάσετε εδώ;

Σπίτι

Εργασία

Άλλο:

*Ποιος είναι ο τελικός προορισμός σας;

Σπίτι

Εργασία

Άλλο:

*Πόσο συχνά κάνετε αυτήν τη μετακίνηση;

Καθημερινά

3-4 φορές την εβδομάδα

1 φορά την εβδομάδα

2-3 φορές το μήνα

Σπανιότερα

Figure A-4: RP Questionnaire – Page 4

*Είστε χρήστης του διαδικτύου;

Ναι Όχι

*Επιθυμείτε να προβείτε σε συμπλήρωση του υπόλοιπου ερωτηματολογίου από το σπίτι σας ή από τον χώρο εργασίας σας εντός διαστήματος 10 ημερών;
Θα χρειαστεί να διαθέσετε περίπου 15 λεπτά.

Σας γνωρίζεται ότι με την υποβολή του υπολοίπου ερωτηματολογίου, μπαίνετε στην κλήρωση για να διεκδικήσετε δωροεπιταγές των Super market ΣΚΛΑΒΕΝΙΤΗΣ.

Ναι Όχι

Προηγούμενη Υποβολή

Figure A-5: RP Questionnaire – Page 5

Με τη συνέναισή σας, θα χρειαστεί να καταγραφούν:

Μικρό όνομα:

E-mail:

Τηλέφωνο:

Προηγούμενη Υποβολή

Figure A-6: RP Questionnaire – Page 6

Second Phase

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 1

Σας υπενθυμίζεται ότι συμπληρώνοντας το παρόν ερωτηματολόγιο λαμβάνετε μέρος στην κλήρωση των δωροεπιταγών του Supermarket ΣΚΛΑΒΕΝΙΤΗΣ.
Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος συμπλήρωσης είναι τα 15 λεπτά.
Ας ξεκινήσουμε!

***Επισημαίνεται ότι η συμπλήρωση του ερωτηματολογίου γίνεται ανώνυμα, σύμφωνα με τα πρότυπα του GDPR, και τα δεδομένα της ανάλυσης που θα προκύψουν θα χρησιμοποιηθούν μόνο σε ποσοτικές και ποιοτικές αναλύσεις στα πλαίσια των ανωτέρω ερευνητικών σκοπών.**

Συναινείτε; Εάν όχι, απλά κλείνετε τον σύνδεσμο.
Σας γνωρίζεται ότι ακόμα και σε περίπτωση συναίνεσης, έχετε τη δυνατότητα ανάκλησής της εντός 10 ημερών.

Συναινώ

*** Παρακαλώ εισάγετε τον κωδικό συνέντευξης που βρίσκεται στο πάνω δεξιά μέρος της κάρτας που σας δόθηκε:**

*** Ημερομηνία / Ώρα**

*** Σε ποιόν Δήμο βρίσκεται το σπίτι σας;**

Figure A-7: SP Questionnaire – Page 1

* Παρακαλώ βρείτε στον ψηφιακό χάρτη την περιοχή της οικίας σας και υποδείξτε την πλησιέστερη διασταύρωση-τοπωνύμιο με το χεράκι/πινέζα.

Restrict search to map extent

Latitude: Longitude:

* Σε ποιόν Δήμο βρίσκεται ο τόπος εργασίας σας ή σπουδών;

* Παρακαλώ βρείτε στον ψηφιακό χάρτη την περιοχή της εργασίας/χώρου σπουδών σας και υποδείξτε την πλησιέστερη διασταύρωση-τοπωνύμιο με το χεράκι/πινέζα.

Restrict search to map extent

Latitude: Longitude:

Figure A-8: SP Questionnaire – Page 2

* Πόσο συχνά μετακινείστε από το σπίτι σας κάνοντας χρήση του Μετρό/Προαστιακού;

Καθημερινά

3-4 φορές την εβδομάδα

1 φορά την εβδομάδα

2-3 φορές τον μήνα

Σπανιότερα

* Ποιον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού χρησιμοποιείτε στις μετακινήσεις από το σπίτι;

Δουκίσσης Πλακεντίας

Κορωπίου

* Ποιος ήταν ο σκοπός της τελευταίας σας μετακίνησης από το σπίτι με χρήση Μετρό ή Προαστιακού; Επιλέξτε έναν από τους παρακάτω σκοπούς:

Προς την εργασία

Για σπουδές

Προσωπικοί λόγοι (ψώνια, ψυχαγωγία, άθληση, κοινωνικοί λόγοι)

Άλλο:

Figure A-9: SP Questionnaire – Page 3

* Τι ώρα ξεκινήσατε από το σημείο Προέλευσης;

* Ποιο από τα παρακάτω μέσα χρησιμοποιήσατε, ή χρησιμοποιείτε συνήθως, για να φθάσετε στον σταθμό;

Λεωφορείο ΟΑΣΑ

Οδηγός χωρίς συνεπιβάτη με επιβατικό όχημα που σταθμεύω στην περιοχή του σταθμού

Οδηγός με συνεπιβάτη με επιβατικό όχημα που σταθμεύω στην περιοχή του σταθμού

Ταξί

Figure A-10: SP Questionnaire – Page 4

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 2

*Πόσα λεπτά χρειάστηκαν από την πόρτα του σπιτιού σας μέχρι το Σταθμό;

📌 Παρακαλώ συνυπολογίστε στον συνολικό χρόνο και τους χρόνους περπατήματος

*Πόσα λεπτά απο τα παραπάνω χρειάστηκαν μέχρι να βρείτε θέση στάθμευσης;

*Πού σταθμεύσατε;

- Σε δρόμο κοντά στον σταθμό χωρίς πληρωμή
- Σε ανοιχτό χώρο κοντά στον σταθμό χωρίς πληρωμή
- Σε χαρακτηρισμένο χώρο στάθμευσης χωρίς πληρωμή
- Σε χώρο στάθμευσης της ΑΤΤΙΚΟ ΜΕΤΡΟ

Figure A-11: SP Questionnaire – Page 5

*Για πόσες περίπου ώρες παρέμεινε το όχημά σας σταθμευμένο;

*Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε τυχαία έναν αριθμό:

📌 Η επιλογή ενός τυχαίου αριθμού ζητείται για την επιστημονικά ορθή εξαγωγή συμπερασμάτων

- 2
- 3
- 1

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-12: SP Questionnaire – Page 6

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 3

* Πήρατε Μετρό ή Προαστιακό;

- Μετρό
 Προαστιακό

* Πόσα λεπτά χρειάστηκαν μέχρι να έρθει ο συρμός;

* Σε ποιον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού αποβιβάστηκατε από το σύστημα;

* Με ποιο τρόπο συνεχίσατε την μετακίνησή σας μετά την αποβίβασή σας από το Μετρό/Προαστιακό στον τελικό σας προορισμό;

- Με τα πόδια
 Με ταξί
 Ήρθε κάποιος και με πήρε με όχημα
 Με λεωφορείο του ΟΑΣΑ
 Άλλο:

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-13: SP Questionnaire – Page 7

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 4

*Πόσα λεπτά χρειάστηκαν για να φθάσετε στον τελικό σας προορισμό από τη στιγμή που αποβιβασθήκατε από το Μετρό/Προαστιακό;

*Σε ποιόν Δήμο βρίσκεται ο τελικός προορισμός της μετακίνησής σας;

*Παρακαλώ βρείτε στον ψηφιακό χάρτη την περιοχή του τελικού προορισμού σας και υποδείξτε την πλησιέστερη διασταύρωση-τοπωνύμιο με το χεράκι/πινέζα.

Restrict search to map extent

Latitude:

Longitude:

Κάντε κλικ για να ορίσετε τη θέση ή σύρετε και αποθέστε την πινέζα. Μπορείτε επίσης να εισάγετε συντεταγμένες.

Leaflet | Map data © OpenStreetMap contributors, CC-BY-SA

Figure A-14: SP Questionnaire – Page 8

*Πόσα λεπτά ήταν ο συνολικός χρόνος της μετακίνησής σας από το σπίτι στον τελικό σας προορισμό (αφαιρέστε τυχόν χρονικό διάστημα που δεν συμπεριλαμβάνεται στους παραπάνω δηλωθέντες χρόνους, π.χ. στάση για καφέ).

📍 Παρακαλώ συσπολογίστε στον συνολικό χρόνο και το χρόνο περπατήματος

*Ποιο ήταν, σε ευρώ, το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης από το σπίτι στον τελικό σας προορισμό;

📍 Ως κόστος για κάθε μέσο θεωρείται:

Λεωφορεία: Κόστος εισιτηρίου μηδενικό καθότι με το ίδιο εισιτήριο συνεχίζεται η μετακίνηση μέσω Μετρό/Προαστιακού

Μετρό/Προαστιακός: Κόστος εισιτηρίου

Αυτοκίνητο: Κόστος καυσίμου και λειτουργικών εξόδων (~0,5€ χιλιόμετρο) + Κόστος στάθμευσης

Ταξί: Κόστος κομίστρου

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-15: SP Questionnaire – Page 9

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 5

Οι επόμενες ερωτήσεις αφορούν την, εντός της ημέρας, αντίστροφη μετακίνηση δηλαδή την επιστροφή σας στο σπίτι.

* Η επιστροφή στο σπίτι έγινε με τη χρήση Μετρό/Προαστιακού;

Ναι

Όχι

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-16: SP Questionnaire – Page 10

* Από πού ξεκινήσατε για τη μετακίνησή προς το σπίτι σας με χρήση Μετρό/Προαστιακού;

Χώρος εργασίας ή σπουδών

Άλλο:

* Τι ώρα ξεκινήσατε από εκεί;

* Σε ποιον σταθμό επιβιβαστήκατε στο Μετρό/Προαστιακό για την μετακίνηση επιστροφής στο σπίτι;

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε...

* Με ποιο τρόπο φθάσατε στον σταθμό αυτόν του Μετρό/Προαστιακού;

Με τα πόδια

Με ταξί

Με έφερε κάποιος με το αμάξι του

Με λεωφορείο του ΟΑΣΑ

Άλλο:

Figure A-17: SP Questionnaire – Page 11

* Πόσα λεπτά χρειάστηκαν για να φθάσετε στον σταθμό αυτό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού από την προέλευσή σας;

* Χρησιμοποίησατε Μετρό ή Προαστιακό;

Μετρό

Προαστιακό

* Με ποιο μέσο μετακινηθήκατε από τον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού που αποβιβασθήκατε προς το σπίτι σας;

Λεωφορείο ΟΑΣΑ

Οδηγός χωρίς συνεπιβάτες με όχημα που ήταν σταθμευμένο στην περιοχή του σταθμού

Οδηγός με συνεπιβάτες με όχημα που ήταν σταθμευμένο στην περιοχή του σταθμού

Ταξί

Με τα πόδια

Συνεπιβάτης σε όχημα που με παρέλαβε από τον σταθμό

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-18: SP Questionnaire – Page 12

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 6

* Πόσα λεπτά είναι συνήθως ο συνολικός χρόνος από την πλατφόρμα του Μετρό/Προαστιακού μέχρι το σπίτι σας;

Προηγούμενη

Επόμενη

Figure A-19: SP Questionnaire – Page 13

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 7

*Πόσα λεπτά ήταν ο συνολικός χρόνος της μετακίνησής σας από την προέλευσή σας προς το σπίτι σας; (αφαιρέστε τυχόν χρονικό διάστημα που δεν συμπεριλαμβάνεται στους παραπάνω δηλωθέντες χρόνους, πχ στάση για καφέ στον Σταθμό)

*Ποιο ήταν, σε ευρώ, το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης από την προέλευσή σας προς στο σπίτι;

📍 Ως κόστος για κάθε μέσο θεωρείται:

Λεωφορείο: Κόστος εισιτηρίου μηδενικό καθώς με το ίδιο εισιτήριο συνεχίζεται η μετακίνηση μέσω Μετρό/Προαστιακού

Μετρό/Προαστιακό: Κόστος εισιτηρίου

Αυτοκίνητο: Κόστος καυσίμου και λειτουργικών εξόδων (~0,5€ χιλιόμετρο) + Κόστος στάθμευσης

Ταξί: Κόστος κομίστρου

* Τι από τα παρακάτω σας αποθαρρύνει περισσότερο να επιλέξετε τα Μέσα Μαζικής Μεταφοράς για τη μετακίνησή σας στον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού;

📍 Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε 2 απαντήσεις.

- Μικρή συχνότητα δρομολογίων λεωφορείων
- Μεγάλη απόσταση περπατήματος μέχρι τη στάση
- Έκθεση στις καιρικές συνθήκες
- Μεγάλη πλήρότητα λεωφορείων
- Μεγάλος χρόνος διαδρομής λεωφορείων
- Έλλειψη στεγάστρων
- Έλλειψη πληροφόρησης δρομολογίων και εκτάκτων περιστατικών

Figure A-20: SP Questionnaire – Page 14

*Φύλο

Γυναίκα Άνδρας

*Ηλικιακή ομάδα

- 18-25
 26-35
 36-45
 46-55
 56-65
 Άνω των 65

*Ποια είναι η κύρια απασχόλησή σας;

- Μισθωτός Δημόσιου ή Ιδιωτικού Τομέα
 Ελεύθερος Επαγγελματίας
 Επιχειρηματίας/Στέλεχος Επιχείρησης
 Φοιτητής/Σπουδαστής
 Συνταξιούχος
 Οικιακή απασχόληση
 Σε αναζήτηση εργασίας
 Άλλο

Figure A-21: SP Questionnaire – Page 15

*Πόσα μέλη υπάρχουν στο νοικοκυριό σας;

*Πόσα επιβατικά οχήματα διατίθενται προς χρήση στο νοικοκυριό σας;

*Πόσοι συνολικά διαθέτουν άδεια οδήγησης οχήματος στο νοικοκυριό σας;

*Ποιο είναι το μέσο μηνιαίο εισόδημα στο νοικοκυριό σας;

Μέχρι 1000€

1000€ - 1500€

1500€ - 2000€

Άνω των 2000€

Figure A-22: SP Questionnaire – Page 16

*Γνωρίζετε τι είναι ο συνεπιβατισμός;

Ναι Όχι

Συνεπιβατισμός (carpooling/ridesharing) ονομάζεται ο τρόπος μετακίνησης όταν δύο τουλάχιστον άτομα, το ένα ως οδηγός και το/τα άλλο/άλλα ως επιβάτες, που έχουν κοινό ή παραπλήσιο σημείο προέλευσης και κοινό ή παραπλήσιο σημείο προορισμού, μετακινούνται με το όχημα του οδηγού μοιραζόμενοι τις δαπάνες μετακίνησης. Οι δαπάνες αφορούν στο κόστος καυσίμου και συντήρησης του οχήματος που αναλογεί στη συγκεκριμένη μετακίνηση, το κόστος στάθμευσης και το κόστος διοδίων εφόσον υπάρχουν. Ο κάτοχος του οχήματος δεν μπορεί να αποκομίσει οποιοδήποτε κέρδος από τον συνεπιβατισμό. Σε διαφορετική περίπτωση θεωρείται ότι προβαίνει σε εμπορική μίσθωση του οχήματος κάτι που είναι παράνομο. Στον συνεπιβατισμό οι επιβάτες είναι ασφαλισμένοι εφόσον το όχημα είναι κατάλληλα ασφαλισμένο.

Ο συνεπιβατισμός συμβάλλει στην αύξηση της μέσης πληρότητας των οχημάτων και κατ' επέκταση στη μείωση των κινουμένων οχημάτων και στη μείωση των ρύπων στο περιβάλλον. Κίνητρο για τους χρήστες του συνεπιβατισμού είναι η μείωση τους κόστους μετακίνησης για τον κάτοχο του οχήματος και για τους συνεπιβάτες που δεν χρησιμοποιούν το δικό τους όχημα, ενώ για τους συνεπιβάτες είναι επιπλέον η μείωση του χρόνου μετακίνησης και η μεγαλύτερη ευκολία και άνεση.

Ο συνεπιβατισμός συνδυάζεται με άλλα μέτρα όπως η προνομακική στάθμευση των οχημάτων με περισσότερους από ένα άτομο αλλά και διέλευση από λωρίδες οχημάτων υψηλής πλήρωσης.

*Ποια είναι η άποψή σας για τον συνεπιβατισμό;

Πολύ αρνητική
 Αρνητική
 Αδιάφορη
 Θετική
 Πολύ θετική
 Δεν έχω άποψη / Δεν απαντώ

Προηγούμενη Επόμενη

Figure A-23: SP Questionnaire – Page 17

Ανήκετε στην κατάσταση: **Επιβάτης λεωφορείου**

Στο τελευταίο αυτό τμήμα του ερωτηματολογίου σας ζητείται να προβείτε στην βέλτιστη για εσάς επιλογή μεταξύ τριών εναλλακτικών τρόπων μετακίνησης για το τμήμα της μετακίνησής σας **Σπίτι – Σταθμός Μετρό/Προαστιακού**.

Οι τρεις τρόποι μετακίνησης είναι οι ακόλουθοι:

- Η Εναλλακτική 1 η οποία είναι η υπάρχουσα κατάσταση
- Η Εναλλακτική 2 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως οδηγός του οχήματός σας έχοντας ένα συνεπιβάτη που θα παραλάβετε πλησίον του σπιτιού σας και θα αφήσετε στον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης αυτής και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον συνεπιβάτη σας
- Η Εναλλακτική 3 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως συνεπιβάτης ενός διαμοιραζόμενου οχήματος. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον οδηγό του οχήματος

Συνολικά θα σας παρουσιαστούν 8 κάρτες με τους 3 εναλλακτικούς τρόπους μετακίνησης με διαφορετικό κόστος και χρόνο μετακίνησης κάθε φορά, καθώς και με την δυνατότητα ή μη προνομιακής στάθμευσης στον σταθμό για τα διαμοιραζόμενα οχήματα. Η προνομιακή στάθμευση σημαίνει ότι θα έχετε εξασφαλισμένο χώρο στάθμευσης δίπλα στον σταθμό, επομένως θα κερδίσετε τον χρόνο που χρειάζεται κάποιος για να βρει θέση στάθμευσης. Στο κάτω μέρος των καρτών πριν την επιλογή θα δείτε τις απαραίτητες επεξηγήσεις.

Ας αρχίσουμε λοιπόν!

* Ποια από τις 3 εναλλακτικές επιλέγετε;

	Εναλλακτική 1: Υπάρχουσα κατάσταση Επιβάτης λεωφορείου	Εναλλακτική 2: Οδηγός σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο	Εναλλακτική 3: Επιβάτης σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο
Χρόνος σπίτι-σταθμός:	50 λεπτά	25 λεπτά	27 λεπτά
Κόστος σπίτι-σταθμός:	0 ευρώ	3.4 ευρώ	3.4 ευρώ
Προνομιακή Στάθμευση:		Προνομιακή Στάθμευση: Όχι	Σημείο Συνάντησης: Απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
Ευέλκτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:		1 ώρα πριν	3 ώρες πριν

📍 **Προνομιακή στάθμευση (αφορά την εναλλακτική του οδηγού):** Ο οδηγός του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα έχει εγγυημένη θέση στάθμευσης έξω απ' τον σταθμό Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Διαφορετικά θα χρειαστεί να αναζητήσει θέση στάθμευσης.

📍 **Σημείο συνάντησης (αφορά την εναλλακτική του συνεπιβάτη):** Μπορεί να είναι έξω απ' το σπίτι του συνεπιβάτη του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου ή σε απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια.

📍 **Ευέλκτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:** Σε περίπτωση κωλύματος, ο οδηγός ή ο συνεπιβάτης του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα πρέπει να ενημερώσει τον δεύτερο 1, 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν.

📍 Αυτή η ερώτηση είναι υποχρεωτική

Εναλλακτική 1

Εναλλακτική 2

Εναλλακτική 3

Figure A-24: SP Questionnaire – Indicative Game Card for the Category of Bus Users

Ανήκετε στην κατάσταση: Οδηγός αυτοκινήτου χωρίς συνεπιβάτη

Στο τελευταίο αυτό τμήμα του ερωτηματολογίου σας ζητείται να προβείτε στην βέλτιστη για εσάς επιλογή μεταξύ τριών εναλλακτικών τρόπων μετακίνησης για το τμήμα της μετακίνησής σας **Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μετρό/Προαστιακού**.

Οι τρεις τρόποι μετακίνησης είναι οι ακόλουθοι:

- Η Εναλλακτική 1 η οποία είναι η υπάρχουσα κατάσταση
- Η Εναλλακτική 2 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως οδηγός του οχήματός σας έχοντας ένα συνεπιβάτη που θα παραλάβετε πλησίον του σπιτιού σας και θα αφήσετε στον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης αυτής και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον συνεπιβάτη σας
- Η Εναλλακτική 3 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως συνεπιβάτης ενός διαμοιραζόμενου οχήματος. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον οδηγό του οχήματος

Συνολικά θα σας παρουσιασθούν 8 κάρτες με τους 3 εναλλακτικούς τρόπους μετακίνησης με διαφορετικό κόστος και χρόνο μετακίνησης κάθε φορά, καθώς και με την δυνατότητα ή μη προνομιακής στάθμευσης στον σταθμό για τα διαμοιραζόμενα οχήματα. Η προνομιακή στάθμευση σημαίνει ότι θα έχετε εξασφαλισμένο χώρο στάθμευσης δίπλα στον σταθμό, επομένως θα κερδίσετε τον χρόνο που χρειάζεται κάποιος για να βρει θέση στάθμευσης. Στο κάτω μέρος των καρτών πριν την επιλογή θα δείτε τις απαραίτητες εξηγήσεις.

Ας αρχίσουμε λοιπόν!

*** Ποια από τις 3 εναλλακτικές επιλέγετε;**

	Εναλλακτική 1: Υπάρχουσα κατάσταση Οδηγός αυτοκινήτου χωρίς συνεπιβάτη	Εναλλακτική 2: Οδηγός σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο	Εναλλακτική 3: Επιβάτης σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο
Χρόνος σπίτι-σταθμός:	10 Λεπτά	2 Λεπτά	4 Λεπτά
Κόστος σπίτι-σταθμός:	2.5 ευρώ	0.8 ευρώ	0.8 ευρώ
Προνομιακή στάθμευση:		Προνομιακή Στάθμευση: Ναι	Σημείο Συνάντησης: Έξω απ' το σπίτι
Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:		3 ώρες πριν	3 ώρες πριν

❶ **Προνομιακή στάθμευση (αφορά την εναλλακτική του οδηγού):** Ο οδηγός του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα έχει εγγυημένη θέση στάθμευσης έξω απ' τον σταθμό Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Διαφορετικά θα χρειαστεί να αναζητήσει θέση στάθμευσης.

Σημείο συνάντησης (αφορά την εναλλακτική του συνεπιβάτη): Μπορεί να είναι έξω απ' το σπίτι του συνεπιβάτη του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου ή σε απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια.

Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης: Σε περίπτωση κωλύματος, ο οδηγός ή ο συνεπιβάτης του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα πρέπει να ενημερώσει τον δεύτερο 1, 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν.

Εναλλακτική 1

Εναλλακτική 2

Εναλλακτική 3

Figure A-25: SP Questionnaire – Indicative Game Card for the Category of Solo Drivers

Ανήκετε στην κατάσταση: **Οδηγός αυτοκινήτου με συνεπιβάτη**

Στο τελευταίο αυτό τμήμα του ερωτηματολογίου σας ζητείται να προβείτε στην βέλτιστη για εσάς επιλογή μεταξύ τριών εναλλακτικών τρόπων μετακίνησης για το τμήμα της μετακίνησής σας **Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μετρό/Προαστιακού**.

Οι τρεις τρόποι μετακίνησης είναι οι ακόλουθοι:

- Η Εναλλακτική 1 η οποία είναι η υπάρχουσα κατάσταση
- Η Εναλλακτική 2 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως οδηγός του οχήματός σας έχοντας ένα συνεπιβάτη που θα παραλάβετε πλησίον του σπιτιού σας και θα αφήσετε στον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης αυτής και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον συνεπιβάτη σας
- Η Εναλλακτική 3 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως συνεπιβάτης ενός διαμοιραζόμενου οχήματος. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον οδηγό του οχήματος

Συνολικά θα σας παρουσιασθούν 8 κάρτες με τους 3 εναλλακτικούς τρόπους μετακίνησης με διαφορετικό κόστος και χρόνο μετακίνησης κάθε φορά, καθώς και με την δυνατότητα ή μη προνομιακής στάθμευσης στον σταθμό για τα διαμοιραζόμενα οχήματα. Η προνομιακή στάθμευση σημαίνει ότι θα έχετε εξασφαλισμένο χώρο στάθμευσης δίπλα στον σταθμό, επομένως θα κερδίσετε τον χρόνο που χρειάζεται κάποιος για να βρει θέση στάθμευσης. Στο κάτω μέρος των καρτών πριν την επιλογή θα δείτε τις απαραίτητες επεξηγήσεις.

Ας αρχίσουμε λοιπόν!

* Ποια από τις 3 εναλλακτικές επιλέγετε;

	Εναλλακτική 1: Υπάρχουσα κατάσταση Οδηγός αυτοκινήτου με συνεπιβάτη	Εναλλακτική 2: Οδηγός σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο	Εναλλακτική 3: Επιβάτης σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο
Χρόνος σπίτι-σταθμός:	80 λεπτά	4 λεπτά	2 λεπτά
Κόστος σπίτι-σταθμός:	20 ευρώ	10 ευρώ	7.5 ευρώ
Προνομιακή στάθμευση:		Προνομιακή Στάθμευση: Όχι	Σημείο Συνάντησης: Έξω απ' το σπίτι
Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:		12 ώρες πριν	1 ώρα πριν

📌 **Προνομιακή στάθμευση (αφορά την εναλλακτική του οδηγού):** Ο οδηγός του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα έχει εγγυημένη θέση στάθμευσης έξω απ' τον σταθμό Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Διαφορετικά θα χρειαστεί να αναζητήσει θέση στάθμευσης.

📌 **Σημείο συνάντησης (αφορά την εναλλακτική του συνεπιβάτη):** Μπορεί να είναι έξω απ' το σπίτι του συνεπιβάτη του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου ή σε απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια.

📌 **Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:** Σε περίπτωση κωλύματος, ο οδηγός ή ο συνεπιβάτης του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα πρέπει να ενημερώσει τον δεύτερο 1, 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν.

📌 Αυτή η ερώτηση είναι υποχρεωτική

Εναλλακτική 1

Εναλλακτική 2

Εναλλακτική 3

Figure A-26: SP Questionnaire – Indicative Game Card for the Category of Drivers with Riders

Ανήκете στην κατάσταση: **Επιβάτης ταξί**

Στο τελευταίο αυτό τμήμα του ερωτηματολογίου σας ζητείται να προβείτε στην βέλτιστη για εσάς επιλογή μεταξύ τριών εναλλακτικών τρόπων μετακίνησης για το τμήμα της μετακίνησής σας **Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μετρό/Προαστιακού**.

Οι τρεις τρόποι μετακίνησης είναι οι ακόλουθοι:

- Η Εναλλακτική 1 η οποία είναι η υπάρχουσα κατάσταση
- Η Εναλλακτική 2 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως οδηγός του οχήματός σας έχοντας ένα συνεπιβάτη που θα παραλάβετε πλησίον του σπιτιού σας και θα αφήσετε στον σταθμό του Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης αυτής και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον συνεπιβάτη σας
- Η Εναλλακτική 3 σύμφωνα με την οποία θα μετακινηθείτε ως συνεπιβάτης ενός διαμοιραζόμενου οχήματος. Το συνολικό κόστος της μετακίνησης και το μισό του κόστους στάθμευσης στον σταθμό θα το μοιραστείτε με τον οδηγό του οχήματος

Συνολικά θα σας παρουσιασθούν 8 κάρτες με τους 3 εναλλακτικούς τρόπους μετακίνησης με διαφορετικό κόστος και χρόνο μετακίνησης κάθε φορά, καθώς και με την δυνατότητα ή μη προνομιακής στάθμευσης στον σταθμό για τα διαμοιραζόμενα οχήματα. Η προνομιακή στάθμευση σημαίνει ότι θα έχετε εξασφαλισμένο χώρο στάθμευσης δίπλα στον σταθμό, επομένως θα κερδίζετε τον χρόνο που χρειάζεται κάποιος για να βρει θέση στάθμευσης. Στο κάτω μέρος των καρτών πριν την επιλογή θα δείτε τις απαραίτητες επεξηγήσεις.

Ας αρχίσουμε λοιπόν!

* Ποια από τις 3 εναλλακτικές επιλέγετε;

	Εναλλακτική 1: Υπάρχουσα κατάσταση Επιβάτης ταξί	Εναλλακτική 2: Οδηγός σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο	Εναλλακτική 3: Επιβάτης σε διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο
Χρόνος σπίτι σταθμός:	50 λεπτά	50 λεπτά	54 λεπτά
Κόστος σπίτι-σταθμός:	20 ευρώ	7.8 ευρώ	6.2 ευρώ
Προνομιακή στάθμευση:		Προνομιακή Στάθμευση: Όχι	Σημείο Συνάντησης: Απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:		12 ώρες πριν	3 ώρες πριν

📌 **Προνομιακή στάθμευση (αφορά την εναλλακτική του οδηγού):** Ο οδηγός του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα έχει εγγυημένη θέση στάθμευσης έξω απ' τον σταθμό Μετρό/Προαστιακού. Διαφορετικά θα χρειαστεί να αναζητήσει θέση στάθμευσης.

📌 **Σημείο συνάντησης (αφορά την εναλλακτική του συνεπιβάτη):** Μπορεί να είναι έξω απ' το σπίτι του συνεπιβάτη του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου ή σε απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια.

📌 **Ευέλικτο πρόγραμμα μετακίνησης:** Σε περίπτωση κωλύματος, ο οδηγός ή ο συνεπιβάτης του διαμοιραζόμενου αυτοκινήτου θα πρέπει να ενημερώσει τον δεύτερο 1, 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν.

📌 Αυτή η ερώτηση είναι υποχρεωτική

Εναλλακτική 1

Εναλλακτική 2

Εναλλακτική 3

Figure A-27: SP Questionnaire – Indicative Game Card for the Category of Taxi Users

ΣΕΛΙΔΑ 10

Σας υπενθυμίζουμε ότι στην πιλοτική δοκιμή της εφαρμογής RIDE2RAIL για το συνεπιβατισμό, που προγραμματίζεται να πραγματοποιηθεί τις δύο πρώτες εβδομάδες του Ιουλίου 2022, θα δοθούν δώρα σε όσους συμμετέχουν είτε ως οδηγοί ΙΧ με το όχημά τους είτε ως επιβάτες ΙΧ άλλου ιδιοκτήτη.

Παρακαλούμε, εισάγετε το e-mail σας εάν συναινείτε να επικοινωνήσει η Αττικό Μετρό μαζί σας για να σας ενημερώσει περαιτέρω σχετικά με την πιλοτική δοκιμή της εφαρμογής RIDE2RAIL για το συνεπιβατισμό, την ενδεχόμενη συμμετοχή του ως οδηγός ή επιβάτης ΙΧ και τα αντίστοιχα δώρα (αξίας 50€ για οδηγούς και 30€ για επιβάτες ΙΧ).

E-mail

Πατώντας **Υποβολή** κάτω δεξιά, ολοκληρώνεται η συμπλήρωση του ερωτηματολογίου.

Έτσι, λαμβάνετε αυτόματα μέρος στην κλήρωση για τις δωροεπιταγές των Super Market ΣΚΛΑΒΕΝΙΤΗΣ. Η κληρωτίδα θα συμπληρωθεί με τον κωδικό συνέντευξής σας.

Για να ενημερωθείτε για τους όρους της κλήρωσης που θα γίνει στις 15 Σεπτεμβρίου 2022, αλλά και τους νικητές μπορείτε να επισκεφθείτε τη σελίδα www.poiinde.gr ή εναλλακτικά να εισάγετε το e-mail σας παρακάτω και θα επικοινωνήσουμε εμείς μαζί σας.

Σε περίπτωση που ήδη εισάγατε το mail σας στην παραπάνω ερώτηση, μπορείτε να το αφήσετε εδώ κενό.

Σας ευχαριστούμε θερμά για τον χρόνο σας!

Καλή τύχη στην κλήρωση!

E-mail

Προηγούμενη

Υποβολή

Figure A-28: SP Questionnaire – Last Page

APPENDIX B: Calculation Formulas of Trip Attribute levels for SP games

Table A1: Calculation of Trip Attribute levels for SP games for Category 1 (Bus User)

KAT1	FM Bus						
		ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΣΑ ΚΑΤΑΣΤΑΣΗ	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 1 CARPOOL DRIVER - CPD	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 2 CARPOOL RIDER - CPR	ΤΙΜΗ
1		Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π Το δηλώνει ο ίδιος στη Σελίδα 2 της τελική φάσης του ερωτηματολογίου.	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	50%*TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	50%*TTT_FM
2		Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π Η τιμή αυτή είναι πάντα 0 (καθότι το κόστος εισιτηρίου επιμερίζεται στη μετεπιβίβαση του στο Μετρό/Προαστιακό.	0	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/20+1,5	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/20+1,5
3				Προνομακή Στάθμευση	ΝΑΙ ή ΟΧΙ	Σημείο Συνάντησης	Έξω απ' το σπίτι ή απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
4				Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν	Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν
Με βάση τα παραπάνω θα δημιουργηθούν 24 κάρτες παιχνιδιών χωρισμένες σε 3 blocks των 8 για την ΚΑΤ1 (χρήστες λεωφορείου) σύμφωνα με τους συνδυασμούς που φαίνονται στο φύλο Combinations							
Θεωρούμε ότι το αυτοκίνητο καλύπτει την ίδια απόσταση στον μισό χρόνο από ότι το λεωφορείο. Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Low (L) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές Medium (M) και High (H) προστίθενται 2 και 4 λεπτά αντίστοιχα.							
Θεωρούμε ότι για το λεωφορείο, τα 10 λεπτά χρόνου (χρόνος περπατήματος μέχρι τη στάση + χρόνος εντός λεωφορείου μαζί με στάσεις) αντιστοιχούν σε απόσταση 2 χιλιομέτρων. Θεωρούμε κόστος αυτοκινήτου (καύσιμα, service, ανταλλακτικά) ίσο με 0,5€ ανά χιλιόμετρο. Καθότι είναι 2 άτομα στο διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο, το διαιρούμε με το 2. Τέλος θεωρούμε μέση τιμή κόστους στάθμευσης τα 6€. Διαιρώντας το με το 4 (δία του 2 καθώς αφορά τη μισή μετακίνηση και δια του 2 καθώς το μοιράζονται 2 άτομα) βγαίνει το 1,5€ που προστίθεται στο τέλος. Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Medium (M) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές High (H) και Low (L) προστίθεται ή αφαιρείται το 25% του τελικού αριθμού αντίστοιχα.							

Table A2: Calculation of Trip Attribute levels for SP games for Category 2 (Solo Driver)

KAT2	FM Solo Driver						
		ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΣΑ ΚΑΤΑΣΤΑΣΗ	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 1 CARPOOL DRIVER - CPD	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 2 CARPOOL RIDER - CPR	ΤΙΜΗ
1		Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π Το δηλώνει ο ίδιος στη Σελίδα 2 της τελική φάσης του ερωτηματολογίου.	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π	TTT_FM
2		Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/4+Park_C/2	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+Park_C/4	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός M/Π δια 2	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+Park_C/4
3				Προνομακή Στάθμευση	ΝΑΙ ή ΟΧΙ	Σημείο Συνάντησης	Έξω απ' το σπίτι ή απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
4				Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν	Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν
<p>Με βάση τα παραπάνω θα δημιουργηθούν 24 κάρτες παιχνιδιών χωρισμένες σε 3 blocks των 8 για την KAT1 (χρήστες λεωφορείου) σύμφωνα με τους συνδυασμούς που φαίνονται στο φύλο Combinations</p> <p>Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Low (L) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές Medium (M) και High (H) προστίθενται 2 και 4 λεπτά αντίστοιχα.</p> <p>Θεωρούμε ότι για το αυτοκίνητο, τα 10 λεπτά χρόνου (χρόνος περπατήματος μέχρι το αυτοκίνητο + χρόνος εντός αυτοκινήτου) αντιστοιχούν σε απόσταση 5 χιλιομέτρων. Θεωρούμε κόστος αυτοκινήτου (καύσιμα, service, ανταλλακτικά) ίσο με 0,5€ ανά χιλιόμετρο. Τέλος προσθέτουμε το κόστος στάθμευσης που μας δηλώνει στη σελίδα 2 και το διαιρούμε με το 2 καθώς επιμερίζεται στη μισή μετακίνηση.</p> <p>Με τις παραδοχές που πήραμε κατά τη διαμόρφωση του TC_FM, διαιρούμε την τιμή δια του 2 καθώς το μοιράζονται 2 άτομα. Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Medium (M) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές High (H) και Low (L) προστίθεται ή αφαιρείται το 25% του τελικού αριθμού αντίστοιχα.</p>							

Table A3: Calculation of Trip Attribute levels for SP games for Category 3 (HOV Driver)

KAT3 FM Driver with Passenger							
	ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΣΑ ΚΑΤΑΣΤΑΣΗ	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 1 CARPOOL DRIVER - CPD	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 2 CARPOOL RIDER - CPR	ΤΙΜΗ	
1	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π Το δηλώνει ο ίδιος στη Σελίδα 2 της τελική φάσης του ερωτηματολογίου.	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TTT_FM	
2	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/4+Park_C/2	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+Park_C/4	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π δια 2	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+Park_C/4	
3			Προνομακή Στάθμευση	ΝΑΙ ή ΟΧΙ	Σημείο Συνάντησης		Έξω απ' το σπίτι ή απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
4			Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν	Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαίτηση για ενημέρωση		1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν
<p>Με βάση τα παραπάνω θα δημιουργηθούν 24 κάρτες παιγνίων χωρισμένες σε 3 blocks των 8 για την KAT1 (χρήστες λεωφορείου) σύμφωνα με τους συνδυασμούς που φαίνονται στο φύλο Combinations</p> <p>Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Low (L) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές Medium (M) και High (H) προστίθενται 2 και 4 λεπτά αντίστοιχα.</p> <p>Θεωρούμε ότι για το αυτοκίνητο, τα 10 λεπτά χρόνου (χρόνος περπατήματος μέχρι το αυτοκίνητο + χρόνος εντός αυτοκινήτου) αντιστοιχούν σε απόσταση 5 χιλιομέτρων. Θεωρούμε κόστος αυτοκινήτου (καύσιμα, service, ανταλλακτικά) ίσο με 0,5€ ανά χιλιόμετρο. Τέλος προσθέτουμε το κόστος στάθμευσης που μας δηλώνει στη σελίδα 2 και το διαιρούμε με το 2 καθώς επιμερίζεται στη μισή μετακίνηση.</p> <p>Με τις παραδοχές που πήραμε κατά τη διαμόρφωση του TC_FM, διαιρούμε την τιμή δια του 2 καθώς το μοιράζονται 2 άτομα. Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Medium (M) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές High (H) και Low (L) προστίθεται ή αφαιρείται το 25% του τελικού αριθμού αντίστοιχα.</p>							

Table A4: Calculation of Trip Attribute levels for SP games for Category 4 (Taxi User)

KAT4	FM Taxi						
		ΥΠΑΡΧΟΥΣΑ ΚΑΤΑΣΤΑΣΗ	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 1 CARPOOL DRIVER - CPD	ΤΙΜΗ	ΕΝΑΛΛΑΚΤΙΚΗ 2 CARPOOL RIDER - CPR	ΤΙΜΗ
1		Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π Το δηλώνει ο ίδιος στη Σελίδα 2 της τελική φάσης του ερωτηματολογίου.	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TTT_FM	Συνολικός Χρόνος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TTT_FM
2		Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π Το κόστος του ταξί που δηλώνει ο ίδιος στη Σελίδα 2 της τελική φάσης του ερωτηματολογίου.	TC_TAXI_FM	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+1,5	Συνολικό Κόστος Σπίτι - Σταθμός Μ/Π δια 2	TC_FM=TTT_FM/8+1,5
3				Προνομαική Στάθμευση	ΝΑΙ ή ΟΧΙ	Σημείο Συνάντησης	Έξω απ' το σπίτι ή απόσταση 2-4 λεπτά με τα πόδια
4				Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαιτήση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν	Ευέλικτο Πρόγραμμα Μετακίνησης - Απαιτήση για ενημέρωση	1, ή 3 ή 12 ώρες πριν
<p>Με βάση τα παραπάνω θα δημιουργηθούν 24 κάρτες παιγνίων χωρισμένες σε 3 blocks των 8 για την KAT1 (χρήστες λεωφορείου) σύμφωνα με τους συνδυασμούς που φαίνονται στο φύλο Combinations</p> <p>Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Low (L) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές Medium (M) και High (H) προστίθενται 2 και 4 λεπτά αντίστοιχα.</p> <p>Θεωρούμε ότι για το αυτοκίνητο, τα 10 λεπτά χρόνου (χρόνος περπατήματος μέχρι τη αυτοκίνητο + χρόνος εντός αυτοκινήτου) αντιστοιχούν σε απόσταση 5 χιλιομέτρων. Θεωρούμε κόστος αυτοκινήτου (καύσιμα, service, ανταλλακτικά) ίσο με 0,5€ ανά χιλιόμετρο. Καθότι είναι 2 άτομα στο διαμοιραζόμενο αυτοκίνητο, το διαιρούμε με το 2. Τέλος θεωρούμε μέση τιμή κόστους στάθμευσης τα 6€. Διαιρώντας το με το 4 (για του 2 καθώς αφορά τη μισή μετακίνηση και δια του 2 καθώς το μοιράζονται 2 άτομα) βγαίνει το 1,5€ που προστίθεται στο τέλος. Καθώς αυτή η τιμή αντιπροσωπεύει το Medium (M) στους συνδυασμούς μας, για τις τιμές High (H) και Low (L) προστίθεται ή αφαιρείται το 25% του τελικού αριθμού αντίστοιχα.</p>							

APPENDIX C: Data Protection Information and Agreement Declaration

ΔΗΛΩΣΗ ΕΝΗΜΕΡΩΣΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΠΑΡΟΧΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΑΤΑΘΕΣΗΣ ΓΙΑ ΤΑ ΠΡΟΣΩΠΙΚΑ ΔΕΔΟΜΕΝΑ ΣΑΣ

Σκοπός

Τα προσωπικά σας δεδομένα που συλλέγονται στο πλαίσιο της παρούσας έρευνας, θα χρησιμοποιηθούν από την Εταιρεία POLINDE Ε.Ε. η οποία αποτελεί "Εκτελών την Επεξεργασία" για λογαριασμό της **ΑΤΤΙΚΟ ΜΕΤΡΟ Μονοπρόσωπη Α.Ε.** αποκλειστικά για τη διεξαγωγή έρευνας με αντικείμενο τη διερεύνηση χρήσης συνεπιβατισμού στο πρώτο /τελευταίο σκέλος μετακινήσεων με αστικό σιδηρόδρομο στην ευρύτερη περιοχή Αθηνών, στο πλαίσιο του ευρωπαϊκού ερευνητικού έργου RIDE2RAIL (881825).

Επιβεβαιώνω ότι:

- έχω διαβάσει το παρόν έντυπο συγκατάθεσης μετά από ενημέρωση για αυτήν την έρευνα,
- είχα την ευκαιρία να κάνω ερωτήσεις σχετικά με την έρευνα και είμαι ικανοποιημένος/η με τις απαντήσεις και τις επεξηγήσεις που μου δόθηκαν ,
- μου δόθηκε ο χρόνος και η ευκαιρία να διαβάσω τις πληροφορίες προσεκτικά και να αποφασίσω αν θα συμμετάσχω στην έρευνα αυτή,
- έχω κατανοήσει ότι οι πληροφορίες που θα παρέχω σε αυτήν την έρευνα θα καταγραφούν, αλλά τελικά δεν θα μπορούν να ταυτοποιηθούν με εμένα, καθώς η διαχείρισή τους θα διασφαλίζει την ανωνυμία μου,
- κατανοώ πως αν κατά τη διάρκεια της συνέντευξης αποχωρήσω από την έρευνα τα δεδομένα μου θα διαγραφούν,
- κατανοώ ότι εντός δύο (2) εβδομάδων από τη λήψη της συνέντευξης μπορώ να ζητήσω να διαγραφούν τα δεδομένα μου. Μετά το πέρας των δύο (2) εβδομάδων ούτως ή άλλως θα έχουν ανωνυμοποιηθεί.
- έχω ενημερωθεί ότι για τυχόν παράπονα ή καταγγελίες σχετικά με οποιοδήποτε στοιχείο της διαδικασίας θα πρέπει να επικοινωνήσω αποστέλλοντας email στην ηλεκτρονική διεύθυνση info@rolinde.gr, ενώ για τυχόν παράπονα ή καταγγελίες σχετικά με τη διαχείριση προσωπικών δεδομένων μπορώ να επικοινωνήσω με την Αρχή Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα (complaints@dpa.gr).

Υπεύθυνος Επεξεργασίας

ΑΤΤΙΚΟ ΜΕΤΡΟ Α.Ε., Λεωφ. Μεσογείων 191-193, ΤΚ 11525, Αθήνα, 210 6792004

Νομικό Πλαίσιο

Κανονισμός (ΕΕ) 2016/679 του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου της 27/4/2016, Νόμος 4624/2019 περί Αρχής Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα.

Δικαιώματα

Δικαίωμα πρόσβασης, διόρθωσης, διαγραφής, περιορισμού και εναντίωσης της επεξεργασίας. Προκειμένου να ασκήσετε τα δικαιώματά σας μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε αποστέλλοντας email στην ηλεκτρονική διεύθυνση info@polinde.gr εντός δύο (2) εβδομάδων από τη λήψη της συνέντευξης, διότι μετά την πάροδο της διορίας αυτής τα στοιχεία θα έχουν ήδη ανωνυμοποιηθεί, οπότε δεν υπάρχει η δυνατότητα ταυτοποίησης.

Σε κάθε περίπτωση έχετε το δικαίωμα να προσφύγετε στην **Αρχή Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα**, εφόσον θεωρείτε ότι θίγονται τα δικαιώματά σας.

Συμφωνώ με τα ανωτέρω. Ναι [] Όχι []

Ημερομηνία: _____

Ονοματεπώνυμο: _____

Υπογραφή: _____

APPENDIX D: List of Phase A and Phase B variables in Survey Data Set

Table C1 below shows the variable names, their labels and their value type, included in the survey forms and the data sets created.

Table C1: Description of questionnaire variables

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
Phase A			
ID	Answer ID	Open-ended	Scale
ID_2	Interview ID (unique alphanumeric code)	Open-ended	Scale
DATE_A_TIME_A	Interview Date and Time	Open-ended	Scale
STATION_A	Station of Interview	1 = "Doukissis Plakentias" 2 = "Koropi"	Nominal
LOC_A	Location of Interview	1 = "Metro/Suburban Railway Station Platform" 2 = "Ticket Purchasing Place inside the Station" 3 = "Parking Spaces" 4 = "Station Adjacent Roads"	Nominal
DR_LIC	Driver's Licence ownership	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
VEH_OWN	Private Vehicle ownership	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
PT_CARD_OWN	OASA Card ownership	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
PT_CARD	Type of PT Card	1 = "Monthly" 2 = "Quarterly" 3 = "Semi-Annual" 4 = "Annual" 5 = "Anonymous Rechargeable Card"	Ordinal
TRIP_PURP_A	Trip Purpose	1 = "Commuting" 2 = "Study" 3 = "Personal Reasons" 4 = "Return Home" 5 = "Business" 6 = "Other"	Nominal
BOARD_W	Boarding Metro or Suburban Rail	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
ARR_MOD_A	Trip mode of Arrival	1 = "Bus" 2 = "Drive Alone" 3 = "Drive with other passengers" 4 = "Taxi" 5 = "Metro" 6 = "Suburban Rail" 7 = "Walk" 8 = "Private vehicle as a Passenger" 9 = "Other"	Nominal

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
IN_ORIG_A	Trip Origin	1 = "Home" 2 = "Work" 3 = "Other"	Nominal
FIN_DEST_A	Trip Destination	1 = "Home" 2 = "Work" 3 = "Other"	Nominal
TRIP_FRE_A	Trip Frequency	1 = "Daily" 2 = "3-4 times a week" 3 = "Once a week" 4 = "2-3 times a month" 5 = "Rarely"	Ordinal
INTER_A	Internet User	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
COMPL_Q_A	Complete the rest of the questionnaire	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
Phase B			
ID	Answer ID	Open-ended	Scale
ID_2	Interview ID (unique alphanumeric code)	Open-ended	Scale
DATE_B	Interview Date and Time	Open-ended	Scale
HOME_LOC	Home Location	Open-ended	Nominal
WORK_LOC	Work or Study Location	Open-ended	Nominal
TRIP_H_FRE_B	Trip Frequency (for trips with home origin) with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Daily" 2 = "3-4 times a week" 3 = "Once a week" 4 = "2-3 times a month" 5 = "Rarely"	Ordinal
STATION_B	Station (for trips with home origin) with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Doukissis Plakentias" 2 = "Koropi"	Nominal
TRIP_PUR_H_B	Trip Purpose (for trips with home origin) with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Commuting" 2 = "Study" 3 = "Personal Reasons" 4 = "Other"	Nominal
DEP_T_H_B	Origin Departure Time	Open-ended	Scale
TR_MD_FM_B	Transport Mode First Mile Phase B	1 = "Bus" 2 = "SOV" 3 = "HOV" 4 = "Taxi"	Nominal
ROUTE_NO_FM	Bus Line	Open-ended	Nominal
BUS_STOP_HOME	Bus Stop	Open-ended	Nominal
TT_H_PLA_FM_BUS	Travel Time Home-Platform First Mile for Bus	Open-ended	Nominal
TT_H_TERM_FM_K1	Travel Time Home-Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
PST_TERM_FM_K1	Parking Search Time Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
PARK_LOC_K1	Parking Location Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers	1 = "On-street near the station without payment" 2 = "Off-street near the station without payment" 3 = "Parking lot without payment" 4 = "ATTIKO METRO parking lot"	Nominal
PARK_TC_K1	Parking Cost Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
PARK_DUR_K1	Parking Duration Terminal First Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
TT_H_TERM_FM_K2	Travel Time Home-Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
PST_TERM_FM_K2	Parking Search Time Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
PARK_LOC_K2	Parking Location Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers	1 = "On-street near the station without payment" 2 = "Off-street near the station without payment" 3 = "Parking lot without payment" 4 = "ATTIKO METRO parking lot"	Nominal
PARK_TC_K2	Parking Cost Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
PARK_DUR_K2	Parking Duration Terminal First Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
TTT_FM_TAXI	Total Travel Time Home-Platform First Mile for Taxi	Open-ended	Scale
TC_TAXI_FM	Taxi Cost First Mile	Open-ended	Scale
TRAIN_SEL_OUT	Metro or Suburban Outward	1 = "Metro" 2 = "Suburban Rail"	Nominal
WAT_PLA_OUT	Waiting platform time	Open-ended	Scale
STAT_OFF_OUT_B	Station outward Ingress	Open-ended	Scale
TR_MD_OUT_ING	Transport mode outward Ingress	1 = "On foot" 2 = "Taxi" 3 = "Pick up & Ride" 4 = "Bus" 5 = "Other"	Nominal
TT_ING	Travel Time Station-Destination Outward	Open-ended	Scale
FD_TRIP_OUT	Final Trip Destination	Open-ended	Scale
TT_OD_OUT	Travel Time Origin-Destination	Open-ended	Scale

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
TC_OD_OUT	Travel Cost Origin-Destination	Open-ended	Scale
RH_TRAIN_SEL	Return Home with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
TRIP_OR_IN	Trip Origin Ingress with Metro/Suburban	1 = "Work or Study Location" 2 = "Other"	Nominal
DEP_T_RH_B	Departure Time Return Home	Open-ended	Scale
STAT_ON_RH	Station Onboard Return Home	Open-ended	Scale
TR_MD_STA_RH	Transport Mode to Station Return Home	1 = "On foot" 2 = "Taxi" 3 = "Pick up & Ride" 4 = "Bus" 5 = "Other"	Nominal
TTT_OR_STAT_RH	Total Travel Time Origin-Station Return Home	Open-ended	Scale
TRAIN_SEL_RH	Metro or Suburban Return Home	1 = "Metro" 2 = "Suburban Rail"	Nominal
TR_MD_LM_RH	Transport Mode Last Mile Return home	1 = "Bus" 2 = "SOV" 3 = "HOV" 4 = "Taxi" 5 = "On foot" 6 = "Pick up & Ride"	Nominal
TT_PLA_H_LM_BUS	Travel Time Platform-Home Last Mile for Bus	Open-ended	Scale
WLK_PLA_VEH_K1_LM	Walking Time Platform Vehicle Last Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
IVT_PARK_HPARK_K1_LM	In Vehicle Time Terminal Park-Home Park Last Mile for SOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
WLK_PLA_VEH_K2_LM	Walking Time Platform Vehicle Last Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
IVT_PARK_HPARK_K2_LM	In Vehicle Time Terminal Park-Home Park Last Mile for HOV Drivers	Open-ended	Scale
WAT_TAXI_LM	Waiting Time for Taxi Last Mile	Open-ended	Scale
TAXI_IVT_TERM_H_LM	In Vehicle Taxi Time Terminal-Home Last Mile	Open-ended	Scale
WAT_PU_TERM_LM	Waiting Time Pick Up at Terminal Last Mile	Open-ended	Scale
PU_IVT_TERM_H_LM	In Vehicle Time Pick Up at Terminal Last Mile	Open-ended	Scale
TTT_OD_RH	Total Travel Time Origin-Destination Return Home	Open-ended	Scale
TC_OD_RH	Travel Cost Origin-	Open-ended	Scale

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
	Destination Return Home		
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_FREQ	Low Bus Frequency	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_WALK_DISTANCE	Long Walking Distance to Bus Stop	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_WEATHER	Exposure to Weather Conditions	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_CROWD	High Bus Occupancy	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_TIME	Long Bus Journey Time	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_SHELTER	Lack of Shelters	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MOST_IMP_PR_BUS_INFO	Lack of Timetable and Emergency Information	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
SEX	Gender	1 = "Woman" 2 = "Man"	Nominal
AGE_GR	Age Group	1 = "18-25" 2 = "26-35" 3 = "36-45" 4 = "46-55" 5 = "56-65" 6 = "> 65"	Ordinal
OCCUP	Occupation	1 = "Public/Private Sector Employee" 2 = "Freelancer" 3 = "Entrepreneur/ Employer" 4 = "Student" 5 = "Retired" 6 = "Housekeeping" 7 = "Looking for a job" 8 = "Other"	Nominal
HH_SIZE	Number of Household Members	Open-ended	Scale
HH_VEH	Number of Private Vehicles in Household	Open-ended	Scale
HH_LIC	Number of Household Members with Driving Licence	Open-ended	Scale
HH_INC	Average Monthly Household Income	1 = "< 1000€" 2 = "1000€ – 1500€" 3 = "1500€ – 2000€" 4 = ">2000€"	Ordinal
KNOW_CARPOOLING	Knowledge about Carpooling	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
OPINION_CARPPooling	Personal Opinion about Carpooling	1 = "Very Negative" 2 = "Negative" 3 = "Neutral" 4 = "Positive" 5 = "Very Positive"	Ordinal

Name	Label	Values	Type of Variable
USER	Type of user	1 = "Bus" 2 = "SOV" 3 = "HOV" 4 = "Taxi"	Nominal
CHOICE	Choice of users	1 = "Current" 2 = "Carpool Driver" 3 = "Carpool Rider"	Nominal
TIME	Travel Time Home – Station assigned to each alternative	Open-ended	Scale
COST	Travel Cost Home Station assigned to each alternative	Open-ended	Scale
PARK	Preferential Parking assigned to each alternative	1 = "Yes" 2 = "No"	Nominal
MEETING	Meeting Point assigned to each alternative	1 = "Home" 2 = "Out of Home"	Nominal
FLEX	Flexible time assigned to each alternative	1 = "1 hour before" 2 = "3 hours before" 3 = "12 hours before"	Ordinal